

GEMMA Generation IV Materials Maturity

Grant Agreement N°: 755269

D4.11: Modelling and microstructure investigations of the corrosion damage Final Report

Work Package	Deliverable number	Lead contractor	Date	
WP4.4	D4.11	ENEA	29. 11. 2021	
Responsible person details				
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Starting date	Due date	Actual date	Delay*	Nature
28. 2. 2020	30. 11. 2021			R
Description of the activities:				
<p>This document reports on the activities carried out in the frame of the Task 4.4 of the GEMMA project and relative to modelling and target experiments on steel compatibility with lead and LBE melts. The microstructure of FeCr and FeCrNi model alloys exposed to lead alloy melts has been characterized and the results compared with the data obtained on technological steels in order to assess the influence of the composition of the alloy on the corrosion behavior. The interpretation of the data is supported by thermodynamic data and atomistic modelling.</p> <p>Contributors: E. Ricci¹, R. Novakovich¹, M. Navas², A. Hojna³, E. Macerata⁴, M. Mariani⁴, A. Tsybanev⁵, K. Gladinez⁵</p> <p>¹ CNR Italy, ² CIEMAT, ³ CVR, ⁴ POLIMI, ⁵ SCK CEN</p>				
SIGNATURES				
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1 INTRODUCTION AND OBJECTIVES

Corrosion of metallic materials is the degradation produced by a chemical (eventually electrochemical) reaction with the surrounding environment. Apart from gold, platinum and a few “noble metals”, the other metals never occur in their pure form and normally are bound to other chemical elements in form of oxides, sulphides etc. and produced in the pure form by using the technique of the extractive metallurgy. All metals (with the exceptions abovementioned) react more or less violently with the environmental oxygen and develop a thin strata of oxide, which protects them from corrosion and makes them appear shiny. The main technique for the protection of metal alloys from corrosion is based on this fact: adding “less noble” metals to the alloy that form a thin passive film by reacting with the chemicals contained in the environment. In stainless steels, a thin self-healing layer of oxide rich in chromium which passivates the surface, realizes corrosion protection.

All corrosion processes are associated with the loss of protection by the passivating oxide due to reactions with the environment and according to different mechanisms. The phenomenology observed in the case of steels exposed to heavy liquid metals is the formation of a double oxide scale formed by an internal FeCr oxide and an external one of magnetite. The dual oxide layer results protective at intermediate temperatures but at high temperature, above 450°C, it is usually observed the growth of a thick oxide not stable and with poor adhesion with the steel substrate, which quickly detaches leaving the metal exposed to the liquid metal. The direct contact of the steels with the liquid metal leads to the selective dissolution of the alloying elements in the melt. The actual corrosion process in HLM is indeed the dissolution of the steel leading, depending on the boundary conditions to severe damage to the structures.

It is usually reported that all the steel elements show a certain solubility in HLM but the dissolution regards mainly nickel in molten lead and Ni and to a lesser extent chromium in lead bismuth eutectic. The dissolution attack reaches penetration thicknesses, which depend of temperature, temperature gradient in the system, oxygen concentration, presence of contamination in the melt and the geometry and distribution of the temperature in the loop. In given boundary conditions, the attack depends on the composition of the steels resulting worse by increasing the nickel content and the microstructure, i.e. grain size presence of extensive defects. The dissolutive process, if not counter-acted, proceeds at the speed of 200 microns/year at a temperature of 550 ° C for a typical austenitic steel exposed to liquid lead at concentration of 10-7 wt% oxygen.

To date, after two decades of research, a very accurate description of corrosion processes in HLM has been given but the mechanisms of the loss of oxide protection are not entirely clear.

This report presents the results on the works performed within GEMMA Task 4.4. devoted to the study of the oxidation and corrosion process in molten lead and lead bismuth eutectic and aimed to study the influence of the minor alloying elements and oxygen concentration on the corrosion process in HLM's. FeCr and FeCrNi model alloys have been exposed to molten Pb and PbBi varying the temperature, oxygen concentration and time of exposure and the microstructure of the corrosion damage has been characterized. Moreover, the study included a comprehensive overview of the available thermodynamic and structural data for the mixed oxides of steel constituents and HLM as well as atomistic simulations.

The activities performed per partner have been as follows:

ENEA: corrosion testing of FeCr and FeCrNi model alloys in LBE with 10-5wt.% oxygen concentration and 1000, 2000, 5000, 8000h times of exposure (T4.1). The specimens after the exposure to the LBE have been characterized by optical and scanning electron microscopy.

CNR: corrosion testing of FeCr and FeCrNi model alloys in LBE with 10-5wt. oxygen concentration and 50, 100, 200, 500 h times of exposure (T4.1). The specimens after the exposure to the LBE have been characterized by scanning electron microscopy. CNR carried out also a comprehensive overview of the available thermodynamic and structural data for mixed oxides of the steel components with lead and lead bismuth.

CVR: corrosion testing of FeCr and FeCrNi model alloys in molten lead with 10-5wt.% oxygen concentration and 50, 100, 200, 500, 1000 h times of exposure. The specimens after the exposure to the lead have been characterized by optical and scanning electron microscopy. , FIB-SEM, WDX, EBSD and SIMS characterizations.

CIEMAT: corrosion testing of FeCr and FeCrNi model alloys in molten LBE for 1000 h at 500°C and 10-5, 10-7, 10-8 wt.% 1000h oxygen concentration. The specimens after the exposure to the LBE have been characterized by optical and scanning electron microscopy SEM-EDX.

POLIMI: modelling of the Fe-Cr-O-Pb-Bi system and its subsystems by means of first principle calculations to gain structural and compositional information about the phases that form in the oxide layer, their stability and their behaviour towards the mass transport.

SCK-CEN: Theoretical and experimental investigation on the interaction of iron and oxygen in molten lead and lead bismuth eutectic.

2 EXPERIMENTAL

2.1 MODEL ALLOYS

Plates of Fe-Cr and Fe-Cr-Ni model alloys have been commissioned to Centro Sviluppo Materiali S.p.A. The two alloys have been produced by vacuum induction melting (VIM) followed by re-melting and casting under vacuum into ceramic preforms with the shape of slabs. The ingots produced were chemically analysed before re-melting and casting in shape. Chemical analyses highlighted the achievement of the required compositions. In Table 1 and 2 the chemical composition of the FeCr cast (BZ1261 cast) and FeCrNi cast (BZ1262 cast).

		COMPOSIZIONE CHIMICA [%]															
		Fe	Ni	Cu	Cr	W	Mo	Nb	Al	Ti	Si	Mn	P	C	S	O	N
<i>min</i>	<i>bal</i>				16,00												
<i>max</i>	<i>bal</i>				18,00												
<i>aim</i>	<i>bal</i>	<0,05			17,00				<0,03		<0,05		<0,05	<0,05	<0,01		
<i>real</i>	<i>bal</i>	<0,05			16,90				<0,03		<0,05		<0,05	<0,01	<0,002		

Table 1. Chemical composition of the BZ1261 FeCr cast

		COMPOSIZIONE CHIMICA [%]															
		Fe	Ni	Cu	Cr	W	Mo	Nb	Al	Ti	Si	Mn	P	C	S	O	N
<i>min</i>	<i>bal</i>	12,00			16,00												
<i>max</i>	<i>bal</i>	14,00			18,00												
<i>aim</i>	<i>bal</i>	13,00			17,00				<0,03		<0,05		<0,05	<0,05	<0,01		
<i>real</i>	<i>bal</i>	12,80			17,10				<0,03		<0,05		<0,05	<0,01	<0,002		

Table 2. Chemical composition of the BZ1262 FeCrNi cast

The slabs produced have been then machined to get a regular thickness of 1,5 mm and 3 mm.

2.2 CORROSION TESTS IN HLM

Samples of the two model alloys have been shipped to the participants to the task according to the testing plan in Table 3 below. The times of exposure and oxygen concentration of the tests have been chosen in order to get a well-developed oxide suitable for the microstructural characterizations.

	Environment	Material	Temperature	[O] wt. %	Time h
CIEMAT	LBE	FeCrNi	500°C	$10^{-5}, 10^{-7}, 10^{-8}$	1000
CNR	LBE	FeCr, FeCrNi	450°C, 550°C	10^{-5}	50, 100, 200, 500
ENEA	LBE	FeCr, FeCrNi	450°C, 550°C	10^{-6}	49, 64, 94, 200, 1000, 2500, 5000
CVR	Pb	FeCr, FeCrNi	450°C, 550°C	10^{-7}	50, 100, 200, 500, 1000

Table 3. Corrosion testing plan

2.3 CHARACTERIZATIONS

The samples exposed to the HLM have been characterized by the participating partners according to the scheme below:

- ENEA, SEM-EDS, optical microscopy
- CVR SEM-EDS
- CNR SEM-EDS
- CIEMAT SEM-EDS

The characterizations have been focussed to the assessment of the following features:

- Composition profiles by SEM EDS in x-section along the normal to the interface by EDS of the oxide, of the internal oxidation zone, of the substrate steel
- Morphology by SEM plane view and x-section:
 - General morphology, Shape (equiassic, columnar...) and size of the grains.
 - Thickness of the oxide
 - Presence of a single or dual oxide and eventually thickness of the layers
 - Internal oxidation no/yes,
 - Presence of a denuded zone at the interface with the steel (pore belt) no/yes,
 - Thickness of the pore belt
 - Max and average thickness of the dissolution layer and penetration of the lead

3 TESTS IN LEAD BISMUTH EUTECTIC

3.1 ENEA

The samples of model alloys were cut out from the plates with dimensions 40x8x3 mm and the surfaces were prepared by standard polishing method using grinding paper up to 1 μm finish. Before the exposure in liquid LBE, the samples were cleaned in acetone in ultrasonic bath.

The exposure tests in liquid LBE have been performed in large stainless steel capsules (Figure 1 below) designed for operations up to 750°C. The capsules consist of a stainless steel cylinder in AISI 321 (h= 500 mm), heated on the outer surface by a furnace. An alumina crucible (d = 110 mm, h = 220 mm) is located at the bottom of the steel cylinder for the containment of the liquid metal; alumina is used to prevent the contact with the steel walls of the capsule and the contamination that would follow. Solid pieces of LBE (about 5.5 Kg) have been introduced inside the alumina crucible, then melted and heated up to the working temperature (heating rate 0.5 °C/min). Before heating the LBE at the working temperature, the solid slugs floating on the free surface have been removed with a steel tool when the temperature is close to melting point (around 170°C). This procedure is performed to minimize the impurities coming from the starting LBE ingots.

The coverlid is equipped with penetrations for the insertion of:

- A K-type thermocouple inside an alumina one-end closed tube,
- An alumina open tube for the gas bubbling in the melt,

- fitting for the outgas,
- oxygen sensor and
- specimen holder-bars for the immersion of the specimens in the liquid melt.

Figure 1 The stainless steel capsules used for the exposure tests in liquid LBE

A spirometallic seal is used to ensure the tightness between the steel cylinder and the cover flange in the capsules during the tests.

The specimen-holder bars were made of AISI 316 steel during tests of FeCrNi model alloy samples and low-alloyed Fe steel during tests of FeCr model alloy samples.

Oxygen sensors made with YPSZ tube solid electrolyte (L = 700 mm) and air reference electrode were used to monitor the oxygen concentration in the melt during the test. The graph in Figure 2 shows the electric potential output of the sensor vs. the oxygen concentration. The oxygen concentration management has been realized with an automatic system by Ar-H₂ or Ar-air gas mixtures injection in the melt based on the feedback given by the potential difference at the electrodes of the oxygen sensor. The total gas flow-rate to the capsules is kept at max. 10 cc/min to avoid violent bubbling and spread of liquid metal on the inner wall of the cylinder.

Figure 2: Air-based oxygen sensor potential as a function of LBE temperature with indication of the oxygen iso-concentration lines (expressed in wt.%) and of the Pb/PbO and Fe/Fe₃O₄ equilibria.

Due to the need to investigate deeper some aspect the complete list of tests has been increased with exposures at the shorter times respect to what stated at the beginning of the project. The complete list of tests is in Table 4 below.

n.	Material	Exp. Time	Exp. T/°C
1	FeCrNi	1000h	450
2	FeCrNi	1000h	450
3	FeCrNi	2500h	450
5	FeCrNi	5000h	450
7	FeCrNi	49h	450
8	FeCrNi	1000 h	550
9	FeCrNi	1000 h	550
10	FeCrNi	2500 h	550
11	FeCrNi	2500 h	550
12	FeCrNi	5000 h	550
13	FeCrNi	64h	550
14	FeCrNi	94h	550
15	FeCrNi	200h	550
16	FeCrNi	49h	550

n.	Material	Exp. Time	Exp. T/°C
1	FeCr	1000h	450
2	FeCr	2500h	450
3	FeCr	5064h	450
4	FeCr	1000h	550
6	FeCr	1000h	550
7	FeCr	2545h	550
8	FeCr	2545h	550
9	FeCr	5014 h	550

Table 4: The complete list of tests is in LBE performed by ENEA

Results of corrosion tests at T= 450 °C:

FeCr Alloy

Typical images of the surface and cross section appearance are shown in the figures below.

Figure 3 FeCr 450°C, 1000h – The oxide layer has thickness below the resolution limit of the microscope. Oxygen is detected only in the LBE residuals. No penetration of LBE in the alloy.

Figure 4 FeCr 450°C, 2500h – CS Polished side. Very thin oxide with thickness around 700nm. No penetration of LBE in the alloy.

Figure 5 FeCr 450°C, 2500h – CS Polished side. Very thin oxide with thickness around 700nm. Some spots with failure of the FeCr oxide and growth of the external magnetite.

Figure 6 FeCr 450°C, 5000h –Very thin oxide with thickness around 700 nm. Same feature seen at 2500h, spots with failure of the FeCr oxide and growth of the external magnetite.

Figure 7 FeCr 450°C, 5000h –Very thin oxide with thickness around 700nm. Same feature seen @ 2500h, spots with failure of the FeCr oxide and growth of the external magnetite.

Respect to the samples exposed for 2500h the sample at 5000h shows, below the magnetite rosettes, a region of internal oxidation right below the FeCr oxide (spot 3 in the micrograph). The spots with the double oxide layer have the innermost area (spot 2 and 3) that is enriched in chromium.

FeCrNi Alloy

Figure 8 FeCrNi 450°C, 46h – Very thin oxide with detachments. Local dissolution attack with depletion of Ni and Chromium.

Figure 9 FeCrNi 450°C, 1000h – Very thin oxide with detachments. Extended dissolution attack with depletion of Ni and Chromium.

Figure 10 FeCrNi 450°C, 2500h – Severe dissolution attack with depletion of Ni and Chromium and thickness in the range 200-250 μ m.

The dissolution zone in all the observations on FeCrNi alloys is totally depleted in Ni with a sharp decrease from the nominal composition to zero. The Cr dissolution is more gradual and at 2500h start from the start of Ni depletion at 18%wt Cr to 5-6%wt to the sample's surface at 6%wt. In the nickel-depleted area are often observed zones enriched in Cr and other in Fe and non-in evident relationship with the dissolution process and probably due to the spinodal decomposition of the FeCr matrix.

Figure 11 FeCrNi 450°C, 5000h – Severe dissolution attack with depletion of Ni and Chromium and thickness in the range 200-250 μm. In the area penetrated by the PbBi is there a depletion of Ni and Cr, even if the latter has areas of enrichment, probable due to the spinodal decomposition of the FeCr alloy after Ni leaching or to carbide precipitates along the line-scan

Results of corrosion tests at T= 550 °C:

FeCr Alloy

Figure 12 FeCr 550°C, 1000h – Typical scenario: infiltration LBE with a depth 7-10 μm accompanied by a depletion in Cr, no oxidation of the metal. The zone depleted in Cr extends well beyond the infiltration limit of LBE. Islands of Cr oxide are observed at the steel-LBE interface, usually submerged by LBE (the native oxide floating).

Figure 13 FeCr 550°C, 2500h – The line scan shows the Cr rich oxide layer and below the penetration zone of the Pb in the sample, which in this case reaches thicknesses of the order of 20-30 μm.

Figure 14 FeCr 550°C, 5000h – Penetration zone of the Pb in the sample, which in this case reaches thicknesses of the order of 40-50 μm .

FeCrNi Alloy

Figure 15 FeCrNi 550°C, 49h – Residual dual layer oxide on the surface, with thickness of approx. 1.5-1.7 μm . No dissolution attack and the concentration of Ni and Cr is close to the nominal one even close to the surface.

Figure 16 FeCrNi 550°C, 64h –Severe dissolution attack with depletion of Ni and Chromium, thickness of the dissolution zone in the range 200-250 μm. In the area penetrated by the PbBi there is total depletion of Ni. The Cr dissolution is more gradual and reaches zero concentration at about 20 μm from the surface.

Figure 17 FeCrNi 550°C, 2500h (left) e 5000h (right) – Optical micrograph showing a severe dissolution attack with thickness about 500-600 μm at 2500h of exposure. At 5000h of exposure the dissolution zone affects the all the thickness of the sample (1,5 mm).

Figure 18 FeCrNi 550°C, 5000h Figure 16: FeCrNi 550°C, 64h – Severe dissolution attack with depletion of Ni ill over the thickness of the sample. The Cr dissolution is more gradual and decreases approaching the surface. The thickness of the Cr total depletion zone in the range 200-250 μm.

Figure 19 FeCrNi 550°C, 5000h Figure SEM at different magnification of the same region – Severe dissolution attack with depletion of Ni and Cr. The FeCrNi slab has become a sort of Fe-based metal sponge.

Summary of the results for FeCr and FeCrNi Alloys in lead

FeCr model alloy: summary of the measurements

- Measurements performed on samples exposed at 450°C it was observed the presence of a very thin oxide slowly growing & no dissolution attack at any time. The oxide resulted protective at all the times of exposure
- Nevertheless, increasing the time of exposure and starting at 2500h it was observed the development of spots spread all over the sample surface where there was a change in the oxidation mechanism and a dual layer oxide developed
- The magnetite spots have circular shape and looks like rosettes over the FeCr oxide that covers the sample
- In the magnetite spots, below the FeCr layer growing inward it was observed the development of an internal oxidation zone
- Outside of the dual layer spots, the growth rate of the oxide in 18 Cr alloy is much slower than the rate of 9Cr F/M steels (F82H, EM10, P91) reported in the literature
- Increasing the temperature at 550°C it was observed the failure of the the oxide and the start of the dissolution attack
- Characterization have been performed in both samples polished, according to the procedure described above, and samples not polished. It was generally observed a similar behavior with same corrosion rate with a delay in the non-polished samples.
- No dissolution reported for the same material in the same experimental campaign by CVR in Pb

FeCrNi model alloy: summary of the measurements

- At the two temperatures tested the dissolution attack started after a very short time of exposure
- The dissolution measured as depth of the zone penetrated by the LBE is faster increasing the temperature
- Both Ni and Cr are leached by the LBE, the Cr dissolution is slower and a decreasing trend in going toward the surface is observed in the Ni depleted zone
- The Corrosion rates of the model alloy result much higher compared with the data reported in the literature for the 316 SS
- The dissolution rate observed in the FeCrNi alloy is much higher than that measured in the FeCr alloy. Higher than 1500 μm at 5000h for FeCrNi vs 50 μm vs measured in FeCr.
- Characterization have been performed in both samples polished, according to the procedure described above, and samples not polished. It was generally observed a similar behavior with same corrosion rate with a delay in the non-polished samples.
- No dissolution reported for the same material in the same experimental campaign by CVR in Pb

3.2 CNR

Specimens of 20 x 5 x 3 mm size were obtained starting from the FeCr (17.5 Cr wt. %) and FeCrNi (17.1Cr, 12.8Ni, wt. %) plates provided by ENEA. Each specimen was fitted with an internal 3mm thread that allowed its connection to the sample holder used for introducing the specimens into the LBE bath. The two parallel face of each specimen have different surface finish: one side was as received (not polished), while the other one was polished down to 1 μ m. The specimens were dipped into the liquid metal bath for about 2/3 of their length. The corrosion test setup used has been already described in the Report: "H2020 GEMMA Task 4.1 Collective exercise". The steel samples were immersed in the liquid metal bath by the push-pull feed-through only when the atmosphere inside the chamber and the desired temperature were reached. After the required exposure time, the samples were pulled out from the bath and the apparatus was cooled. The oxygen content was monitored in the liquid metal bath by a Pt / air oxygen sensor. A reducing Ar-5% H₂ gas mixture (NOXAL Air-Liquide) was used as a cover gas.

About 150 g of LBE alloy was pre-melted in a graphite crucible at T= 650 K under vacuum ($P_{tot} = 0.1$ Pa) for 1 h, then mechanically scratched; rinsed in alcohol; cut in small pieces and placed into the Al₂O₃ crucible ($V_{Cr}=22$ cm³; $V_{LBE} \sim 15$ cm³). The experimental procedure can be summarized as follows:

- I. high purity Ar-5%H₂ gas was purged in the test chamber and a pre-conditioning of LBE was performed at T= 873 K;
- II. The gas flow was established = 0.02 l/s, by a precision leak valve;
- III. The temperature was decreased to the Temperature of the test (TT);
- IV. The samples were maintained at TT under equilibrium conditions for the selected exposure time;
- V. The samples were pulled off the LBE bath and the bath was cooled down.

For each time span and temperature two samples, namely, one of Fe Cr and one of FeCrNi, were dipped together into the same LBE liquid bath.

To characterize the corrosion damages after exposure to LBE, two transversal cross sections were made.

The cross sections were cold-mounted in Struers resin and then ground with SiC paper (down to 4000 grit) and were subsequently polished using diamond paste (down to 1 μ m). An ultrasonic cleaning in an ethanol bath followed cleaning and polishing.

In Table 5, the operative conditions applied during the corrosion tests on FeCr and FeCrNi samples in LBE liquid bath @ T = 450 and 550 °C and different times are shown.

T (°C)	Time (h)	E (V)	C _o (wt.%)	Remarks
450	50	0,813 ÷ 0,884	10 ⁻⁵ ÷ 10 ⁻⁶	The electrode potential value did not stabilize during the test
	100	0,856	2.5 × 10 ⁻⁶	
	200	0,876	1.3 × 10 ⁻⁶	
	500	0,860 ÷ 0,90723	2,2 × 10 ⁻⁶ ÷ 4.8 × 10 ⁻⁷	The electrode potential gradually increased after the first 200 h and attained its upper value
550	50	0,666 ÷ 0,810	10 ⁻³ ÷ 10 ⁻⁵	The electrode potential value did not stabilize during the test
	100	0,718	2.3 × 10 ⁻⁴	
	200	0,788	3.2 × 10 ⁻⁵	
	500	0,897 ÷ 0,926	1.5 × 10 ⁻⁶ ÷ 6.6 × 10 ⁻⁷	The electrode potential gradually increased after the first 200 h and attained its upper value

Table 5: Operative conditions of corrosion tests.

Results of corrosion tests at T= 450 °C:

FeCr Alloys

The Fe-Cr samples show a great difference in behaviour in relation to their surface finishing. The polished sides show layers of oxides different in composition, while on the unpolished sides, no oxides are detected and only a few microns of Cr concentration gradient are noticeable.

The multiple oxide layer observed, was usually composed by mixed oxides containing both Fe and Cr with variable stoichiometry. No penetration by LBE have been observed.

FeCrNi Alloys

Penetration of LBE was observed in all FeCrNi samples. The thickness of penetration increased with increasing time. In the layer penetrated by LBE, Ni depletion was observed.

The presence of Ni is not observed in the grains surrounded by liquid metal, (maybe the microstructure is no longer the starting austenitic one). Just outside the penetrated layer, the composition is very close to the nominal values (17.1Cr, 12.8Ni, wt.%). Within the Ni-depleted penetrated zone, the concentration of Cr is close to that of the nominal composition, while an enrichment in Fe is observed. No compact oxidized layers are noted. The presence of oxygen is limited to small particles near the interface between the base material and the solidified LBE and within the latter.

In Figure 20 the thickness of the penetration observed in FeCrNi samples immersed in LBE at T= 450°C at different time span is shown.

Figure 20 Average Thickness of the penetration observed in the FeCrNi samples immersed in LBE @ T= 450°C at different time for both polished and not polished sides. The operative conditions applied are shown in Table 5.

As outlined in Table 5, the results obtained at the shortest time, t=50 h, have to be considered as not significant because the oxygen sensor was not stabilized. At the highest time span, t= 500 h, the results obtained cannot be considered relevant for the present study, due the progressive increasing of the measured potential caused by the chemical cleaning occurred to the system. In Table 6, a summary of the SEM observations on samples tested at T= 450°C in LBE at different time of exposure is shown.

T (°C)	Time(h)	Sample	Description	Figure
450	50	FeCr	On the sample, polished side an irregular and incompact double layer of oxides is detected. The outermost layer having a thickness of about 6 μm has stoichiometry (Fe, Cr): O=1:2, the innermost layer is about 3μm thick with stoichiometry 3:1. On the unpolished side of the sample, there is neither oxidation nor LBE penetration but only few microns of Cr concentration gradient.	21,22
		FeCrNi	Slight penetration on both sides having different surface finish; the penetration thickness is lower on the polished side. In both cases, Ni depletion is observed.	23,24
	100	FeCr	On the polished side of the sample, a double layer of oxide with a total thickness of about 5μm is detected. The outermost layer consists of an oxide (Fe, Cr): O with 2:1 stoichiometry, the innermost layer with 1: 1 stoichiometry. Only in some areas of the sample, a mixed oxide with a 3: 2 stoichiometric ratio is detected. No oxidation on the unpolished side. The Cr concentration gradient is about 10 μm thick.	25,26
		FeCrNi	Difference in thickness between the two sides. For the polished one, thickness from few μm to even 300 μm, while on the unpolished side a more regular trend is observed. Ni depletion is still observed.	27,28
	200	FeCr	On the polished side, a double layer of oxide with a total thickness of about 10-20, μm similar to that found on the sample processed for 50 h is detected. As in the other samples, oxidation is not detected on the unpolished side.	29,30
		FeCrNi	Qualitatively very similar to the sample exposed for 100 h. The Cr content within the penetrated area is slightly lower near the interface. The presence of oxygen is very limited. Ni depletion is present.	-
	500	FeCr	The polished side has oxide layers. On the unpolished side, only Cr depletion is observed at a distance of about 10 μm from the surface.	31,32,33
		FeCrNi	The penetration thicknesses become significant and are greater on the not polished side. In the penetrated layer, the presence of LBE at grain boundary is observed. The grains affected by this phenomenon are nickel-free, while just outside the penetrated layer the composition is very similar to the nominal one	34,35

Table 6: Summary of the SEM observations on FeCr and FeCrNi samples tested @ T= 450°C in LBE at different time of exposure.

SEM-EDX data

Figure 21 FeCr polished tested @ T=450°C, t = 50 h

Figure 22 FeCr as received tested @ T=450°C, t = 50 h

Figure 23 FeCrNi polished, tested @ T=450°C, t = 50 h

Figure 24 FeCrNi as received tested @ T=450°C, t = 50 h

Figure 25 FeCr polished, tested @ T=450°C, t = 100 h

Figure 26 FeCr as received tested @ T=450°C, t = 100 h

Figure 27 FeCrNi polished, tested @ T=450°C, t = 100 h

Figure 28 FeCrNi as received tested @ T=450°C, t = 100 h

Figure 29 FeCr polished, tested @ T=450°C, t = 200 h

Figure 30 FeCr as received tested @ T=450°C, t = 200 h

Figure 31 FeCr sample tested @ T=450°C, t = 500 h

Figure 32 FeCr polished, tested @ T=450°C, t = 500 h

Figure 33 FeCr as received tested @ T=450°C, t = 500 h

Figure 34 FeCrNi polished (upper side), tested @T=450°C, t = 500 h

Figure 35 FeCrNi as received tested @ T=450°C, t = 500 h, Co = X wt%

Test at T= 550°C

FeCr Alloys

Figure 36 FeCr as received tested @ T=550°C, t = 50, 100 and 200 h

FeCrNi Alloys

From a qualitative point of view, on the FeCrNi samples processed at $T=550^{\circ}\text{C}$, the effects of different surface finishing are not apparent. The penetration layer is easily observable only in samples with exposure times greater than 200 h. As in the case of samples exposed at 450°C , the grains surrounded by the liquid metal are substantially Ni-free, while the rest have the nominal composition. Thin layers of oxide (in the order of 1 - 2 microns) are found sporadically.

In Figure 37 the penetration thickness observed in the FeCrNi samples immersed in LBE at $T= 550^{\circ}\text{C}$ at different time of exposure is shown.

Figure 37 Thickness of the penetration observed in the FeCrNi samples immersed in LBE at $T= 550^{\circ}\text{C}$ at different time of exposure for both polished and not polished sides

As shown in Table 5, the oxygen content tests performed at $T=550^{\circ}\text{C}$ was slightly higher than that recorded in experiments performed at $T= 450^{\circ}\text{C}$. In the former case, the presence of oxide thin films have been detected. The presence of even thin oxide films inhibits the incisiveness of the penetration. In addition, in this case the results obtained at the shortest time span, $t=50$ h, have to be considered not significant because of the missed stabilization of the oxygen sensor.

At the highest time span, $t= 500$ h, similarly to test performed at $T= 450^{\circ}\text{C}$, the results obtained cannot be considered relevant for the study, due the progressive increasing of the measured potential caused by the chemical cleaning occurred to the system. In table 7, a summary of the SEM observations on the FeCrNi samples tested at $T= 550^{\circ}\text{C}$ in LBE at different time of exposure is shown.

T (°C)	Time (h)	Description	Figure
550	50	On the polished side, few microns of penetration are observed together with a reduction in the Ni content. Also the Cr content appears to be reduced. Oxidized phases (stoichiometric ratio (Fe, Cr): O = 1:1) at the interface between LBE and matrix are also observed. On the unpolished side, no oxides are detected.	38,39
	100	No evident penetration at the grain boundaries is observed, regardless of the polishing. Instead, oxides of different composition are present at the interface between the base metal and the solidified LBE.	40
	200	Intergranular penetration layer of very variable thickness occurred. The maximum depth of the order of 200 μm is observed on both sides. The layer is substantially Ni-free and enriched in Fe.	41
	500	On the polished side, a non-homogeneous penetration is observed which reaches a maximum value of 380 microns. The grains inside the penetrated layer are substantially Ni-free and have a reduced Cr content. On the unpolished side, the penetration thickness is more homogeneous and can reach a depth of 300 microns.	42

Table 7: Summary of the SEM observations on the FeCrNi samples tested @ T= 450°C in LBE at different time of exposure.

SEM-EDX data

Figure 38 FeCrNi polished, tested @ T=550°C, t = 50 h

Figure 39 FeCrNi as received tested @ T=550°C, t = 50 h

Figure 40 FeCrNi polished, tested @ T=550°C, t = 100 h

Figure 41 FeCrNi as received tested @ T=550°C, t = 200 h

Figure 42 FeCrNi sample tested @ T=550°C, t = 500 h

3.3 CIEMAT

The materials tested in this frame by the CIEMAT has been the FeCrNi Model Alloy provided by ENEA. During the tests, around 2/3 of the standard specimen (those with 25 mm length) was immersed in liquid metal, being the total surface of the exposed sample around 5 cm².

Corrosion tests have been performed under static condition in furnaces with a quartz tube in which several alumina crucibles were placed. Each crucible contained one steel specimen immersed in approximately 40 g of heavy liquid metal (LBE). A schematic representation of the corrosion test setup used is shown in Figure 43.

Figure 43 Experimental setup for static immersion corrosion tests

A mixture of Ar and Ar + 5%H₂ was continuously fed to obtain the required oxygen partial pressure in the liquid metal, by means of H₂/H₂O ratio. The gas mixture was achieved controlling the flow rates of both gases independently and it is passed through water with controlled temperature. This methodology has been previously checked at CIEMAT laboratories with corrosion results in accordance to other literature data [4].

Table 8 summarizes the experimental scope of the tests including the testing conditions. Each specimen was tested with a starting surface finishing based on a polished grit specimen preparation which corresponds to a roughness measurement (Ra) below 1 μm.

	Test	Material	T (°C)	Time (h)	O ₂ (wt.%)
LBE	Immersion furnace tests	FeCrNi	500	1000	10 ⁻⁵
					10 ⁻⁷
					10 ⁻⁸

Table 8: Immersion corrosion tests under static condition

After the immersion test, metallographic specimen was examined to detect and characterize the material degradation along the longitudinal sections of the specimens prepared without removing the

liquid metal over material surfaces with the measurement of the depth (if dissolution) and/or thickness (if oxide layer). Energy Dispersive X-ray analysis were performed to determine the composition of the oxide layers and/or dissolution presence as well as other interesting features.

FeCrNi Alloys

The summary of the material degradation detected on the examined cross sections of FeCrNi Model Alloy tested in LBE at 500 °C and different oxygen contents is given in Table 9. This table includes the widespread degradation over both surfaces; the maximum damage detected which represents the maximum thickness (if oxide) or penetration (if dissolution) and the average size of defects dissolution/oxide layers, calculated as the mean of the measurements of the oxide layer/dissolution.

	FeCrNi Model Alloys		
	10 ⁻⁵ wt.%. Oxide layers	10 ⁻⁷ wt.%. Dissolution	10 ⁻⁸ wt.%. Dissolution
Examination	Oxide layers	Dissolution	Dissolution
Average size (µm)	7.5	49	65
Maximum size (µm)	11	120	110
Maximum root (µm)		209	168

Table 9: The summary of the corrosion damages found on the analysed cross sections of FeCrNi MA

At 10⁻⁵ wt.% oxygen, the widespread corrosion behaviour observed was formation of the oxide layer with different thickness but quite continuous along the surface (Figure 44)

Figure 44 Surface appearance of FeCrNi Model Alloy tested at 10⁻⁵ wt.%, 500 °C, 1000h

Figure 45 shows the element distribution map of the thicker multilayered oxide detected. It consists of a Fe-based outer layer and a Fe-Cr spinel inner layer. Both layers were not a compact oxide layer due to some penetration of LBE eutectic. In addition, some points with a relative slight Ni enrichment was observed obtained below the oxide layer, as consequence of the chromium depletion close to the spinel oxide.

Figure 45 EDX mapping of an oxide in FeCrNi MA tested at 10⁻⁵ wt.%, 500 °C, 1000h

At 10⁻⁷ wt.% oxygen concentration, the widespread corrosion behaviour of FeCrNi MA is the presence of continuous dissolutions with different structures, half of them with rounded appearance and the other with root shape with a high maximum penetration. Figure 46 shows an example of both surface appearances.

Figure 46 Surface appearance of FeCrNi MA tested at 10⁻⁷ wt.%, 500 °C, 1000h

At the lowest oxygen content, the widespread FeCrNi MA behaviour is represented by continuous dissolutions along the surface, most of them with rounded shape (Figure 47). Figures 48 show the element distribution map of material dissolution and LBE penetration.

Figure 47 Surface appearance of FeCrNi MA tested at 10^{-8} wt.%, 500 °C, 1000h

Figure 48 EDX mapping of a round shape dissolution FeCrNi MA tested at 10^{-8} wt.%, 500 °C, 1000h

Figure 49 EDX mapping of FeCrNi MA dissolution (root) tested at 10-8 wt.%, 500 °C, 1000h

Figure 49 shows the element distribution map of the maximum dissolution (in root) detected. The presence of dissolution penetrations (root type) is occasional, in the case of the lowest oxygen concentration, although this is the deepest penetration observed.

Summary of the results of the characterizations on samples of FeCrNi model alloys exposed in LBE varying the oxygen concentration:

The examination of FeCrNi Model Alloys showed the formation of continuous oxide layers at 10^{-5} wt.% while continuous dissolutions were detected at 10^{-7} and 10^{-8} wt.%. At 10^{-7} wt.% dissolutions presented roots or penetrations with LBE, while at 10^{-8} wt.%, material dissolution found were more rounded and with deeper estimated average value with occasional root penetrations. Figure 50 shows a comparison of the corrosion behaviour observed in the examination of FeCrNi Model Alloy tested at different oxygen content.

Figure 50 Surface comparison of FeCrNi MA tested at different oxygen content, 500 °C, 1000h.

Figure 51 summarizes the size of the different defects detected including the average and maximum size of the oxide layer/dissolution defects collected previously.

In the case of the material dissolution and the associated LBE penetrations, the EDX mapping have shown the chromium and nickel dissolution and LBE penetrations. In the case of FeCrNi MA, the material dissolution also showed deep root penetrations.

Figure 51 Effect of oxygen content in FeCrNi MA behaviour tested in LBE at 500 °C during 1000h

The oxygen content has substantial influence on the corrosion behaviour and the FeCrNi Model Alloys show a change in the corrosion mechanism from oxide layer formation to dissolution attack at lower oxygen concentration in the LBE liquid metal.

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4 TESTS IN LEAD (CVR)

The samples of model alloys, 21x10x1,5 mm, were cut with an EDM machine using a brass wire. The sample surfaces were prepared by a standard polishing method up to 1 μm finish (Figure 52 and 53). The original surface of both alloys contained distinctive black points of Fe-Cr-O precipitates as declare the figures. Before installed in the sample holder samples were cleaned in acetone in ultrasonic device.

The experimental setup for the corrosion tests consists of a stainless steel autoclave with an inner alumina (Al_2O_3) crucible. The tank contains approximately 15 kg of Pb, purity 99.98 %. A gas mixture ($\text{Ar}+\text{H}_2$ (6 %) with $\text{Ar}+\text{O}_2$ (10 %)) was used as cover gas. Oxygen sensors based on the $\text{Bi}/\text{Bi}_2\text{O}_3$ reference electrode were used to monitor the oxygen dissolved in the melt. Active oxygen control was ensured by means of automatic mixing of the cover gases based on the oxygen sensor signal.

The set-up has an air lock chamber, where the samples are kept in Ar gas before and after ingress in the testing tank. The air lock chamber and the testing tank are separated by a ball valve. Samples are inserted in holders connected to a movable rod. Figure 54 shows the full set of static tanks in the laboratory.

Figure 52 FeCr alloy surface after polishing up to 1 μm finish

Figure 53 FeCrNi alloy surface after polishing up to 1 μm finish

Figure 54 The experimental apparatus

The experimental procedure has been as follows: Pb was heated up to the target temperature and purged with Ar+H₂ (6 %) gas to reduce the initial oxygen content to 10⁻⁵ wt.%. Only after the oxygen concentration became stable, the samples were introduced in Pb through the air-tight chamber.

The following formula for the calculation of the oxygen concentration was used [Schroer C. et al., 2011], where C₁ = 3.1216 and C₂ = -3819.2 were taken for Pb.

$$\log\left(\frac{c_o}{mass}\right) = C_1 + \frac{C_2}{T/K} - 10.080 \frac{EMF/V}{T/K}$$

The model alloys were exposed for 50h, 100h, 200h, 500h and 1000h at 450 °C and 550 °C. One sample of each alloy was used for each exposure. The graphs in the following figures (55-59) show the temperature (T) and the oxygen concentration (cOx) during the experiments. Data for two temperatures of given period are shown in one graph.

Figure 55 Temperature and Oxygen concentration during the 50 hour exposure of the model alloys (yellow line + green line = 550°C; red line + blue line = 450°C)

Figure 56 Temperature and Oxygen concentration 10-5 wt. % of during the 100 hours exposure of model alloys (yellow line + green line = 550°C; red line + blue line = 450°C)

Figure 57 Temperature and Oxygen concentration during the 200 hour exposure of the model alloys (red + blue lines = 450°C; yellow + green lines = 550°C test of FeCrNi, orange + grey lines = 550°C test of FeCr)

Figure 58 Temperature and Oxygen concentration during the 500 hour exposure of the model alloys (yellow line + green line = 550°C; red line + blue line = 450°C). Data drops owing to short blackouts.

Figure 59 Temperature and Oxygen concentration during the 1000 hour exposure of the model alloys (yellow line + green line = 550°C; red line + blue line = 450°C). Missing data owing to Windows update.

After the exposure to the lead, the specimens were investigated by means of SEM with EDX. The observations were performed without any cleaning of the lead residuals. The outer surface was first, observed by SEM in pane view, and then cross sectional observation have been performed in samples prepared cutting in the middle the laminas along the longest dimension. Thickness of surface oxidation and local Pb penetration was evaluated in 13 equidistant areas along one side of the cross section (red line in figure 60).

Figure 60 Schematic of sample cross section for post test examinations

Results of the corrosion tests at T= 450 °C:

FeCr Alloys

Post-test examination revealed oxidation of the surface depending of temperature and time. Typical images of the surface and cross section appearance are shown in the figures below.

450°C	SEM-BSE cross section	SEM-BSE surface	EDX
50h			
100h	 		

Figure 61 FeCr model alloy sample appearance after the exposure at 450 °C

FeCrNi Alloys

Post-test examination revealed oxidation of the surface depending of temperature and time. Typical images of the surface and cross section appearance are shown in the Figure below.

Figure 62 FeCrNi model alloy sample appearance after the exposure at 450 °C

Results of corrosion tests at T= 550 °C:

FeCr Alloys

550°C	SEM-BSE cross section	SEM-BSE surface	EDX
50h			
100h			

Figure 63 FeCr model alloy sample appearance after the exposure at 550 °C:

FeCrNi Alloys

550°C	SEM-BSE cross section	SEM-BSE surface	EDX
50h			
100h			

Figure 64 FeCrNi model alloy sample appearance after the exposure at 550 °C

Summary of the results for FeCr and FeCrNi Alloys in lead

FeCr model alloy: summary of the measurements

Post-test examination revealed oxidation of the surface depending of temperature and time.

T [°C]	Exposure [hour]	Oxide and damage thickness [μm]														
			1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	Average
450	50	Outer	0.76	0.86	0.77	1.44	1.8	1.2	1.06	1.39	1.01	1.01	1.49	0.84	0	1.05
		Inner	0.62	1.7	0	2.0	1.76	0.76	1.03	0.82	1.03	0.92	1.57	0.7	0	0.99
		Damage	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0.00
	100	Outer	0.73	1.78	2.37	1.54	1.69	0.95	1.35	0.96	2.13	2.9	1.95	1.41	1.84	1.66
		Inner	0.84	1.74	2.43	1.51	0.92	0.84	0.76	1.35	2.2	2	1.98	2.92	2.04	1.66
		Damage	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0.00
	200	Outer	2.68	2.87	1.7	3.42	2.77	1.31	2.25	2.40	2.83	2.81	3.52	2.49	-	2.59
		Inner	1.9	2.8	2.27	2.16	2.51	1.08	1.57	1.88	1.73	2.04	2.6	1.6	-	2.01
		Damage	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	-	0.00
	500	Outer	1.85	1.03	1.9	1.28	1.68	1.73	5.17	0 ¹	1.84	2.05	1.69	1.46	2.36	1.85
		Inner	1.17	1.24	1.29	1.68	0.94	1.78	1.1	0.72	1.54	1.24	0.92	1.14	1.62	1.17
		Damage	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0.00
1000	Outer	3.54	2.32	4.54	4.46	5.09	3.99	0	5.66	2.62	0	3.33	1.61	0	2.88	
	Inner	3.65	2.45	3.31	3.19	5.34	3.8	0	3.49	2.67	0.36	3.81	4.81	0	2.84	
	Damage	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0.00	
550	50	Outer	10.13	8.98	6.89	5.62	4.87	4.65	5.54	6.22	7.59	9.93	9.89	8.95	8.68	7.53
		Inner	6.8	6.95	3.66	3.96	3.62	4.11	2.76	3.42	5.78	1.58	2.9	6.5	8.51	4.66
		Damage	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0.00
	100	Outer	8.97	1.78	6.15	2.46	2.49	1.46	8.7	2.79	2.99	5.49	1.39	1.95	2.97	3.81
		Inner	7.7	2.27	3.73	1.73	2.49	2.24	2.68	3.89	2.27	3.11	1.73	2.22	4.27	3.10
		Damage	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0.00
	200	Outer	10.18	13.54	8.55	13.28	14.85	14.61	15.61	14.61	11.50	8.92	10.04	11.29	-	12.25
		Inner	6.73	8.94	5.76	8.28	8.15	7.99	10.71	11.38	7.92	6.02	7.15	7.56	-	8.05
		Damage	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0 ²	0 ²	-	0.00
	500	Outer	6.72	1.42	0.52	0.43	1.62	0.48	0	1.5	3.84	7.43	8.23	5.88	3.58	3.20
		Inner	5.08	1.67	1.37	0.76	3.79	0.74	0	5.3	4.82	9.21	9.35	5.08	2.67	3.83
		Damage	0	0	0	0.49	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0.04
1000	Outer	7.5	10.97	2.54	0	2.05	2.59	12.50	15.15	7.62	38.22	8.22	29.15	27.63	12.63	
	Inner	5.0	9.87	3.72	7.37	2.03	8.7	30.95	20.54	5.64	45.82	8.51	25.41	32.92	15.88	
	Damage	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0.00	

¹oxide fully peeled out

²between the measurement points, it was observed a single area of local Pb penetration up to 2.71 μm

Table 10: Post-test examination – the oxidation and the damage thickness was evaluated along the longitudinal cross section

FeCrNi model alloy: summary of the measurements

T [°C]	Exposure [hour]	Oxide and damage thickness [µm]														
			1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	Average
450	50	Outer	0.63	0.43	5.29	0.7	0.49	0	0.91	0	0	0	0	0	0	0.63
		Inner	0.08	0.54	0	0	0.38	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0.08
		Damage	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0.00
	100	Outer	0.65	0.76	0.87	0.86	0.79	0.64	0.59	0.82	0.76	1.21	0	0.63	0.43	0.69
		Inner	0.66	0.59	0.97	0.58	0.84	0.43	0.49	0.81	0.86	0.83	0.33	0.65	0.49	0.66
		Damage	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0.00
	200	Outer	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0.99	0	0.95	0	0.16
		Inner	0	0.43	0.52	0.54	0.53	0	0.78	0.59	0.48	0.22	0.32	0	0	0.37
		Damage	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0.00
	500	Outer	0.65	0.46	0.79	0.55	0.52	1.07	0.49	0.62	0.62	0.78	0.5	0.79	-	0.65
		Inner	0.57	0.29	0.54	0.4	1.3	0.49	0.6	0.36	0.63	0.56	0.62	0.63	-	0.58
		Damage	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	-	0.00
1000	Outer	0	0	1.23	1.25	1.82	2.07	0.81	1.11	1.46	1.89	1.14	1.14	1.08	1.15	
	Inner	0	0	0.88	1.03	1.1	1.34	0.83	0.86	1.51	1.18	0.7	0.81	1.69	0.92	
	Damage	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0.00	
550	50	Outer	2.03	1.73	1.28	1.42	1.94	3.14	2.49	3.14	1.99	2.65	1.62	1.84	1.51	2.03
		Inner	1.52	1.29	0.57	0.67	1.42	1.78	2.29	2.28	1.69	0.82	1.41	1.88	1.47	1.52
		Damage	0.00	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0.00
	100	Outer	0.72	0	0 ¹	3.08	0.49	0 ¹	0	0	0	0	0.76	0	2.7	0.72
		Inner	0.26	0	0	1.72	0	0	0	0	0	0	0.55	0	1.08	0.26
		Damage	0.00	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0 ²	0 ²	0	0.00
	200	Outer	1.13	1.3	1.47	3.21	3.52	0	1.7	0	0.7	3.2	0	0	-	1.35
		Inner	0.7	0	0	0	2.81	0	1.3	0	0	0	0	0	-	0.40
		Damage	1.5	3.1	2.44	0.94	1.2	0	0.33	2.29	0.86	1.58	0	2.05	-	1.36
	500	Outer	0	0	0	0	0	1.5	1.89	0.56	0.32	0.41	1.14	1.0	1.57	0.65
		Inner	4.72	0	0	0	0	1.07	1.64	0.36	0.30	1.41	0.9	0.8	1.43	0.97
		Damage	0	0	0	4.8	7.69	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0.96
1000	Outer	5.68	6.04	2.54	0.86	1.19	1.26	0	1.24	2.76	1.82	1.3	0.25	0	1.92	
	Inner	4.97	4.27	2.22	0.92	0.97	1.51	0.97	1.45	3.14	1.77	2.27	0.25	0	1.90	
	Damage	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0.00	

¹oxide fully peeled out

²between the measurement points, it was observed a single area of local Pb penetration up to 48 µm

Table11: Post-test examination -- the oxidation and the damage thickness were evaluated along the longitudinal cross section

5 MODELLING

5.1 FE-CR-O-PB-BI SYSTEM AND ITS SUBSYSTEMS (CNR)

CNR studied the Fe-Cr, Fe-Pb, Cr-Pb, Fe-O and Cr-O binary systems as a part of the Fe-Cr-O-Bi-Pb system and analysed the literature data on these systems. No new thermodynamic experimental data to re-optimize the Fe-Cr, Fe-Pb and Cr-Pb phase diagrams. Concerning the oxide systems, there are a few assessments of the Fe-O and Cr-O, but the final selections of the optimized data will be done with respect to the thermodynamic description of higher order oxide systems in the framework of CALPHAD modeling.

Common problems faced studying the corrosion of steels exposed to heavy liquid metals (HLM) suggest to introduce the model alloys containing two or three principal steel components, such as Fe-Cr or Fe-Cr-Ni. In this way, would be easier to understand the reactions between HLM and structural materials as well as the effects of oxygen content during corrosion testing. Therefore, to approximate the behavior of steels in liquid Pb or Pb-Bi eutectic alloy (LBE), Fe-Cr model alloys containing 18-19 at % Cr have been selected and the study of the Fe-Cr-O-Bi-Pb system and its subsystems is aimed to be performed. Taking into account experimental conditions of the corrosion tests performed on the Fe-Cr model alloys, the phases found experimentally in the temperature range of 573-973 K for the systems investigated will be highlighted.

5.1.1.1 *Thermodynamic models*

Pure elements

The SGTE (Scientific Group Thermodata Europe) data [15] were used for the pure elements, i.e. Fe, Cr and Pb. The Gibbs energies of pure elements in different structural forms are expressed as a function of temperature by conventional polynomial functions using the stable element reference SER convention as

$${}^{\circ}G_i(T) - H_i^{SER}(298.15) = A + BT + CT \cdot \ln T + DT^2 + ET^3 + \frac{F}{T} + \dots + IT^9 \quad (1)$$

where A, B, \dots, I are coefficients obtained by assessing the thermodynamic properties of the element i ; $H_i^{SER}(298.15)$ is the molar enthalpy of pure element i at reference temperature of 298.15 K and in 10^5 Pa pressure.

5.1.1.2 *Solution phases*

The liquid phase, FCC, BCC, HCP... are considered as solid solutions exhibiting complete mixing. The thermodynamic excess functions using the integral Gibbs energy are fitted by the Redlich-Kister polynomials [16], can be written as

$$G^{xs} = x_1 x_2 \sum_i L_i (x_1 - x_2)^i \quad (2)$$

where L_i is a temperature dependent binary interaction parameter calculated from experimental data. Usually, it assumed to be a linear function of the temperature, given in the form

$$L_i = A_{i0} + B_{i1}T \quad (3)$$

i is the order of each polynomial term, beginning with 0.

Fe-Cr

A well-known feature of the Fe-Cr system is the miscibility gap of the BCC (body centered cubic) phase at low temperatures. Inside the miscibility gap, alloys tend to separate or decompose into a Cr-rich bcc phase (α') and an Fe-rich BCC phase (α). Due to this phase separation, Fe-Cr alloys have been found to exhibit an increased hardness and decreased ductility after aging, which is historically known as the "475 °C" embrittlement". For duplex stainless steels, the decomposition and consequent embrittlement of the ferritic phase effectively sets an upper limit for the service temperature.

Until now, there are more than ten different thermodynamic descriptions of the Fe-Cr system available in the literature [1], [2], [3], [4], [5], [6] and are listed in [7]. Lot of experimental data on the BCC, FCC, σ and liquid phase have been reported and used for its phase diagram assessments, although still now, there are some discrepancies between various models used for phase description, for example the magnetic contribution. Xiong et al. [7] have reviewed the thermodynamic properties of the solid and the liquid phases in the Fe-Cr system. The miscibility gap between BCC+BCC' is associated with the occurrence of spinodal decomposition reaction, $\sigma \leftrightarrow \text{BCC} + \text{BCC}'$ at $T=788$ K. This eutectoid reaction may affect the model alloys exposed to Pb or LBE melts. The existence of σ intermediate phase [4], approximately based on AB stoichiometry accounts for the presence of short range ordering in the liquid phase [[8]]. The last re-assessment of the Fe-Cr is recently reported in [9], as shown in Fig. 1. Taking into account that the phase descriptions and model parameters [7] were used in optimization of other Fe-Cr based systems, their data are given in (Table 12).

Figure 65 The Fe-Cr phase diagram re-assessed by [9]

The available thermodynamic data on the Gibbs free energy, the enthalpy of mixing and the activities for the Fe-Cr liquid phase obtained at $T = 1873$ K are analysed and compared to the corresponding theoretical values calculated by the QCA for regular solutions. The Fe-Cr phase diagram indicates that at $T = 1873$ K the corresponding liquid phase exists up to 60 at.% of Cr (Fig. 1) and concerning the alloys with higher Cr content, the calculations refer to an undercooled liquid system. The interactions

between Fe and Cr constituent atoms are weak. A peculiar phenomenon related to an inversion of chemical ordering near the alloy compositions with Cr content of about 10 at % was revealed experimentally by the diffuse neutron scattering and resistivity experiments performed on solid Fe-Cr alloys. Indeed, the Fe rich alloys containing up to 10 at % Cr exhibited a tendency for ordering, while demixing of Fe and Cr was observed in the case of alloys with Cr content higher than 10 at%. The two contributions can be clearly separated and substantiated by Monte Carlo atomistic simulations, but the explanation of this peculiar phenomenon is still incomplete.

It is well known that a density as a physical property of matter is strongly related to the short range ordering and atomic diffusion processes. Similarly, to the previous observations, recent experimental study on the density of Fe-Cr melts also revealed an anomalous behavior in the case of the excess volume. Namely, the excess volume value of the Fe-10 at % Cr alloy is negative, while for the Fe-20 at% Cr alloy as well as for the other alloy compositions with higher Cr content it is positive. This surely affects the microstructural evolution of the corresponding alloys. Taking into account that Fe-Cr model alloys contain up to 19 at. % Cr, these indications may be useful in explanation of results of corrosion tests.

Fe-Pb

Since 1902 the Fe-Pb phase diagram has been assessed few times. The last re-assessment was reported in [12]. The experimental data on the Fe-Pb system are concentrated on the phase diagram measurements. The Fe-Pb phase diagram is characterized by a large liquid phase miscibility gap, a monotectic reaction, two allotropic transformations and an eutectic reaction. FCC, BCC and liquid were considered as substitutional solution phases with a complete mixing of iron and lead in the same sublattice. The system has no intermediate phases and very small mutual solubilities of Fe and Pb. The solubility of solid Fe in liquid Pb is very low at the eutectic invariant reaction that takes place at $T=600.622$ K, i.e. $BCC + L2 \leftrightarrow BCC + FCC$, where L2 is a low temperature liquid phase. This transformation occurs in a temperature range of corrosion tests. The descriptions of the Fe-Pb phases with optimized binary interaction parameters are given in Table 12.

Figure 66 The Fe-Pb phase diagram assessed by [12]

Cr-Pb

Until now, no comprehensive investigations of the binary Cr-Pb system were found in the literature. In the 1988, the last tentative to assess the Cr-Pb phase diagram has been done [88Ven] and it was based on the exploratory thermal analysis and metallographic studies and the solubility measurements of solid Cr in liquid Pb (Fig. 3). No experimental thermodynamic data for the Cr-Pb system found in the literature. An exception represents the solubility data. The diagram is characterized by the absence of intermediate phases and by extensive immiscibility in the liquid state and essential immiscibility in the solid state. According to [10], a liquid miscibility gap exists within a concentration interval with Pb-content ranging between 9 and 43 at % and at the monotectic temperature of about 1743 K. No determinations of the boundaries of the liquid miscibility gap were carried out at higher temperatures because of the high vapor pressure of Pb, of about 10^5 Pa at 2024 K [73Hul]. It is possible that the true monotectic temperature is actually higher than is shown in Fig. 2. The type of low temperature

invariant three-phase equilibrium at 600 K involving L, (Cr), and (Pb) is not yet known. The solubility of solid Cr in liquid Pb was determined in the temperature range 1173 to 1473 K by chemical analysis of the liquid phase. The solubility of solid Cr in liquid Pb at the monotectic $L_1 \leftrightarrow (Cr) + L_2$ and at the three-phase equilibrium $L + (Cr) + (Pb)$ was estimated extrapolating low temperature solubility. An tentative to describe the phases of the Cr-Pb system was done aiming to calculate the Fe-Cr-Pb phase diagram [11] and the parameters are given in Table 12.

Figure 67 The Cr-Pb phase diagram assessed by [10]

Fe-O

In the assessment of the liquid phase in the Fe-O system reported by [17], the associated solution model with the Fe, FeO and FeO_{1.5} species has been applied. The experimental data on the solubility of oxygen in the metallic melt and the experimental data on the extension of the miscibility gap between 2058 and 2233 K were taken into account. A complete miscibility in the liquid phase above 3100 K has been assumed. with the model parameters given in Table 12. Only the phase equilibria and thermodynamic properties of the liquid at higher temperatures of the Fe-O phase diagram [17] differ from those reported in [18]. The thermodynamic properties and the phase equilibria in the range of solid/liquid equilibria are practically identical with those of [18]. The phase diagram of the Fe-O system assessed by [17] and [19] are shown in Figs. 4a and 4b. The last one represents a complete reevaluation of the whole Fe-O phase diagram taking into account the new experimental data. The major solid solution phases are wuestite and spinel, while FCC and BCC iron and hematite, Fe₂O₃ have very narrow

ranges of nonstoichiometry. Metallic and oxide liquids are separated by a very large miscibility gap. The corresponding oxygen-potential vs. temperature diagram for the Fe-O system is shown in Fig. 4c. The structural data of the phases of the Fe-O system are reported in Deliverable D4.9.

Figure 68 4a The Fe-O phase diagram assessed by [17]

Figure 69 4b The Fe-O phase diagram assessed by [19]

Figure 70 The activity of oxygen Fe-O phase diagram assessed by [17]

Cr-O

The reassessment of the Cr-O liquid phase using an associated solution model and the same experimental information as that in [20] has been reported in [[7]]. To reproduce all available experimental information, regular (temperature dependent) and sub-regular (temperature-independent) parameters have been introduced. The monotectic temperature is calculated to be 2160 K. The resulting phase diagram is compared with the phase diagram from [20] and shown in Fig. 5a. Correct reproduction of the phase relations in the vicinity of the BCC + Cr₃O₄ eutectic can be achieved using only the regular temperature-dependent parameter. The second, subregular parameter, has been introduced to locate the critical temperature of the miscibility gap. However, the lack of experimental information concerning the extension of the miscibility gap in liquid chromium, make it impossible to predict reliably the shape and the extension of the miscibility gap in the Cr-O system. The thermodynamic descriptions of the Cr-O phases with the model parameters are given in Table 12. The corresponding oxygen-potential vs. temperature diagram for the Cr-O system is shown in Fig. 5b. The structural data on the phases of the Cr-O system are reported in Deliverable D4.9.

Figure 71 The Cr-O phase diagram assessed by [17]. Dashed lines show the calculations of [20]

Figure 72 The activity of oxygen Cr-O phase diagram assessed by [17]

System / Phase	Model	Parameters $J \cdot mol^{-1}$	Reference
Fe-Cr			[7]
Liquid	(Cr,Fe)	${}^0L_{Cr,Fe}^{Liq} = -5.983 \cdot T$	
		${}^1L_{Cr,Fe}^{Liq} = -384.41 \cdot T$	
BCC (α)	(Cr,Fe)	${}^0L_{Cr,Fe}^{bcc} = 24212.06 - 15.507 \cdot T$	
		${}^1L_{Cr,Fe}^{bcc} = 1664.69 + 0.286 \cdot T$	
		${}^2L_{Cr,Fe}^{bcc} = -13250.88 + 8.252 \cdot T$	
		${}^0\beta_{Cr,Fe}^{bcc} = -0.45$	
		${}^0T_C^{bcc} = 865.5$	
		${}^1T_C^{bcc} = -567.2$	
FCC (γ)	(Cr,Fe)	${}^0L_{Cr,Fe}^{fcc} = 28871.89 - 22.318 \cdot T$	
		${}^1L_{Cr,Fe}^{fcc} = 32711.42 - 18.180 \cdot T$	
σ phase	$(Cr,Fe)_{10}(Cr,Fe)_{20}$	${}^0G_{Cr,Cr}^{\sigma} - 30 \cdot {}^0G_{Cr}^{bcc} = 150000$	

		${}^0G_{Cr,Fe}^\sigma - 10 \cdot {}^0G_{Cr}^{bcc} - 20 \cdot {}^0G_{Fe}^{bcc}$ $= -13807.14 - 10.715 \cdot T$	
		${}^0G_{Fe,Cr}^\sigma - 10 \cdot {}^0G_{Fe}^{bcc} - 20 \cdot {}^0G_{Cr}^{bcc}$ $= 313807.14 + 10.715 \cdot T$	
		${}^0G_{Fe,Fe}^\sigma - 30 \cdot {}^0G_{Fe}^{bcc} = 150000$	
		${}^0L_{Cr,Fe:Cr}^\sigma = {}^0L_{Cr,Fe:Fe}^\sigma = 7722.64 - 139.766 \cdot T$	
		${}^0L_{Cr:Cr,Fe}^\sigma = {}^0L_{Fe:Cr,Fe}^\sigma = 89908.52 - 156.894 \cdot T$	
Cr-Pb			[10]
Liquid	(Cr,Fe)	${}^0L_{Cr,Pb}^{Liq} = 35000$	[11]
		${}^1L_{Cr,Pb}^{Liq} = -15000$	
FCC	(Cr,Fe)	${}^1L_{Cr,Pb}^{fcc} = 100000$	
Fe-Pb			[12]
Liquid	(Fe,Pb)	${}^0L_{Fe,Pb}^{Liq} = 110114.85 - 9.11 \cdot T$	
		${}^1L_{Fe,Pb}^{Liq} = 27699.55 - 6.74 \cdot T$	
BCC	(Fe,Pb)	${}^0L_{Fe,Pb}^{bcc} = 108.25 + 89.00 \cdot T$	
FCC	(Fe,Pb)	${}^0L_{Fe,Pb}^{fcc} = 7.06 + 90.05 \cdot T$	
Pb-O	Reported in Deliverable D4.9		[13]
Bi-O	Reported in Deliverable D4.9		[14]
Fe-O			[7]
Liquid	(Fe,FeO,FeO _{1.5}) ₁	${}^0G_{Fe}^{Liq} - H_{Fe}^{SER} = GFELIQ$	
		${}^0G_{FeO}^{Liq} - H_{Fe}^{SER} - H_O^{SER}$ $= GFEO + 34008$ $- 20.969 \cdot T$	
		${}^0G_{FeO1.5}^{Liq} - H_{Fe}^{SER} - 1.5H_O^{SER}$ $= 0.5GFE2O3 + 39712$ $- 20.007 \cdot T$	
		$L_{Fe,FeO}^{Liq} = 109625.2 - 20.05 \cdot T +$ $(26317.9 - 11.072 \cdot T)(y_{Fe} - y_{FeO})$	
		$L_{Fe,FeO1.5}^{Liq} = 81541.2$	

		$L_{FeO,FeO1.5}^{Liq} = -13353.8 + 6707.07(y_{FeO} - y_{FeO1.5})$	
BCC	(Fe) ₁ (O,Va) ₃	${}^0G_{Fe,Va}^{bcc} - H_{Fe}^{SER} = GHSERFE$	
		${}^0G_{Fe:O}^{bcc} - H_{Fe}^{SER} - 3H_O^{SER} = GHSERFE + 3 \cdot GOSOL$	
		$L_{FeO,Va}^{bcc} = -517549 + 71.83 \cdot T$	
FCC	(Fe) ₁ (O,Va) ₁	${}^0G_{Fe,Va}^{fcc} - H_{Fe}^{SER} = GFEFCC$	
		${}^0G_{Fe:O}^{fcc} - H_{Fe}^{SER} - H_O^{SER} = GFEFCC + GOSOL$	
		$L_{FeO,Va}^{fcc} = -168758 + 19.17 \cdot T$	
GAS	O ₁ ,O ₂ ,O ₃ ,Fe,FeO	${}^0G_O^{Gas} - H_O^{SER} = GO1GAS$	
		${}^0G_{O_2}^{Gas} - 2H_O^{SER} = GO2GAS$	
		${}^0G_{O_3}^{Gas} - 3H_O^{SER} = GO3GAS$	
		${}^0G_{Fe}^{Gas} - 2H_{Fe}^{SER} = GFEGAS$	
		${}^0G_{FeO}^{Gas} - H_{Fe}^{SER} - H_O^{SER} = GFEOGAS$	
Cr-O			[7]
Liquid	(Cr,CrO _{1.5}) ₁	${}^0G_{Cr}^{Liq} - H_{Cr}^{SER} = GCRLIQ$	
		${}^0G_{CrO1.5}^{Liq} - H_{Cr}^{SER} - 1.5H_O^{SER} = 0.5GCR2O3 + 64852 - 24.915 \cdot T$	
		$L_{Cr,CrO1.5}^{Liq} = 78019.5 - 35 \cdot T + 55478 \cdot (y_{Cr} - y_{CrO1.5})$	
BCC	(Cr) ₁ (O,Va) ₃	${}^0G_{Cr,Va}^{bcc} - H_{Cr}^{SER} = GHSERCR$	
		${}^0G_{Cr:O}^{bcc} - H_{Cr}^{SER} - 3H_O^{SER} = GHSERCR + 3 \cdot GOSOL$	
		$L_{CrO,Va}^{bcc} = -673435 + 27.86 \cdot T$	
GAS	O ₁ ,O ₂ ,O ₃ ,Cr,CrO, CrO ₂ , CrO ₃	${}^0G_O^{Gas} - H_O^{SER} = GO1GAS$	
		${}^0G_{O_2}^{Gas} - 2H_O^{SER} = GO2GAS$	
		${}^0G_{O_3}^{Gas} - 3H_O^{SER} = GO3GAS$	

		${}^0G_{Cr}^{Gas} - 2H_{Cr}^{SER} = GCRGAS$	
		${}^0G_{CrO}^{Gas} - H_{Cr}^{SER} - H_O^{SER} = GCROGAS$	
		${}^0G_{CrO_2}^{Gas} - H_{Cr}^{SER} - 2H_O^{SER} = GCRO2GAS$	
		${}^0G_{CrO_3}^{Gas} - H_{Cr}^{SER} - 3H_O^{SER} = GCRO3GAS$	

Table 12 Summary of the optimized thermodynamic parameters of the Fe-Cr, Fe-Pb, Cr-Pb, Fe-O and Cr-O systems

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5.2 DENSITY FUNCTIONAL THEORY CALCULATIONS (POLIMI)

Stability, structure and composition of phases and behavior towards the mass transport

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POLIMI work focused on the development of DFT simulations to gain structural and compositional information about the phases that form in the oxide layer, and on the evaluation of thermodynamic parameters for new mixed oxides.

Density functional theory on condensate phase has been used through the usage of Vienna Ab-Initio Simulation Package (VASP) (G. Kresse et Hafner 1993) (G. Kresse et Furthmüller 1996). This code uses pseudopotential or the projector augmented wave (PAW) method with a plane wave basis set to describe the interaction between atoms. In literature there are many examples of the use of VASP that show the adaption of code on a wide range of applications guaranteeing a good agreement with experimental data but also the possibility to provide some new properties not yet tested on real material that could explain the behaviour of materials.

In order to assess the capability of the approach to estimate with an appropriate accuracy the thermodynamic parameters by means of computed vibrational frequencies and energy contributions, a validation process has been carefully implemented by selecting a series of compounds belonging to the spinel family and comparing the calculated values with the experimental data. The study is addressed to investigate the layers formed at the lead-steel interface, so the approach has been tested on similar compounds found in literature. In particular, eleven spinels have been chosen: chromite (FeCr_2O_4), magnetite (Fe_3O_4), cobalt aluminate blue spinel (CoAl_2O_4), hercynite (FeAl_2O_4), cuprospinel (CuFe_2O_4), trevorite (NiFe_2O_4), franklinite (ZnFe_2O_4), ulvospinel (TiFe_2O_4), galaxite (MnAl_2O_4) e spinel ferrite (AlFe_2O_4). In the validation step, different parameters were used as figures of merit. The percentage deviation/error provides the discrepancy between the calculated and the experimental values giving quantitative information on the quality of the used approach. For the cases under consideration, the values chosen for comparison are the lattice parameters and the trends of enthalpy, entropy and specific heat as a function of temperature.

In general, simulations have been optimized by testing different methods and approaches (GGA, PAW method, Hubbard U method, functionals, basis-set...) on reference compounds and validating them by comparison with experimental data.

5.2.1.1 Validation process

A series of simulation has been conducted in order to select the proper functional which best represents the interactions between the various elements. Among functionals available in VASP have been tested four of them:

- Perdew-Wang (91): it treats analytically the representation of correlation energy for uniform electron gas in order to give a more accurate description for magnetic effects (Perdew et al. 1992).
- Perdew-Burke-Ernzerhof (PBE): it belongs to the family of Generalized gradient approximations but all the parameters are considered fundamental constants (Perdew et al. 1996).
- Revised Perdew-Burke-Ernzerhof (RPBE) with Pade Approximation: this is based on local density approximation (LDA) property using specific functional obtained by other models (Hammer et al. 1999).
- Perdew-Burke-Ernzerhof revised for solid (PBEsol): it is a combination of uniform electron gas surface energy condition for correlation and the gradient expansion for exchange (Csonka et al. 2009).

The next step was to start the simulations and to record in the first place the lattice parameter through the minimization of the ground state energy. After obtaining the geometric optimization of various compounds, vibrational frequencies have been evaluated, allowing the calculation of heat capacity, enthalpy and entropy. The results have been compared with experimental ones reporting a good agreement in the reproducibility of the trend for each compounds with some problem at Curie temperature. The bottleneck has been the evaluation of the enthalpy which strongly depend on functional used in the calculations. On the other hand the lattice parameter is quite independent from the functional. The error has been calculated according to the following formula:

$$Err\% = \frac{(X_{cal} - X_{exp})}{|X_{exp}|} \times 100$$

where X_{cal} and X_{exp} are respectively the calculated and experimental values. The absolute value at the denominator has been introduced for the negative values of enthalpy in order to take the over/under-

estimation of the experimental values. A first evaluation on the best functional is summarized in the

Figure 73. The formation enthalpy at 298.15 K has been calculated from the ground state energy resulting from the simulation and then compared with the experimental values available. For RPBE the percentage error exceeds the 60% demonstrating that it is not suitable for this type of compounds. A same behaviour is registered for the 91 and PBE, but presenting lower range of errors for each compounds. Among the functionals analysed, PBEsol reproduces with a good agreement the experimental data as shown in Table 13.

Figure 73 Percentage error of the studied compound for the different type of available functional

Compounds	H_{exp} [kJmol ⁻¹]	H_{PBEsol} [kJmol ⁻¹]	err%
chromite	-1458.124	-1400.919	3.92
magnetite	-1118.383	-1160.4625	-3.76
hercynite	-1995.299	-1896.1007	4.97
curospinel	-967.968	-1061.781	-9.69
trevorite	-1081.1	-1053.7669	2.52
ulvospinel	-1515.236	-1503.4253	0.77
galaxite	-2098.569	-2007.7434	4.32
spinel	-2299.903	-2264.6647	1.53
franklinite	-1171.579	-1172.1852	-0.05
spinel ferrite	-1955.17	-1843.2194	5.72

Table 13 Comparison between experimental and calculated enthalpies

Table shows the percentage error between lattice parameter calculated with PBEsol and experimental data: the results confirm a well reproducibility of geometry of the crystal structure for the spinel group within a range of error 0.3-3 %.

Compounds	a_{exp} [Å]	a_{cal} [Å]	err%	E [eV]	Crystal structure	N atoms
MgAl ₂ O ₄	8.08	8.16	0.99	-397.4134		
FeCr ₂ O ₄	8.376	8.4255639	0.59	-440.2696		
Fe ₃ O ₄	8.3963	8.424413	0.33	-401.9870		
CoAl ₂ O ₄	8.106	8.16	0.66	-406.0919		
FeAl ₂ O ₄	8.16	8.203	0.52	-418.4686		
CuFe ₂ O ₄	8.37	8.169169	2.39	-379.9775	cF56	56
NiFe ₂ O ₄	8.3378	8.122747	2.57	-393.2083		
ZnFe ₂ O ₄	8.4465	8.198976	2.93	-369.2022		
TiFe ₂ O ₄	8.5352	8.526184	0.1	-453.2501		
MnAl ₂ O ₄	8.2104	8.26641	0.68	-433.9388		
AlFe ₂ O ₄	8.16	8.203	0.52	-418.4686		

Table 14 Crystallographic data of the compounds: a comparison between experimental and calculated lattice parameters

The heat capacity of the different compounds has been evaluated as a function of temperature in the range between 298.15K to 1400K (Figure 74) and in some case, where experimental data were available, it has been calculated starting also from very low temperature 25 K (Figure 74). In all the cases considered, the trend is respected and the errors increase with the temperature where electronic and magnetic effects, not considered in the approach, became important. The percentage errors at 298.15 for each investigated compounds range between 0.05% and 10%.

Figure 74 Heat capacity of chromite (left) and cobalt alluminate blue spinel (right) as a function of temperature: comparison between calculated (blue line) and experimental (red points) values.

The enthalpy evaluated with statistical thermodynamics show the capacity of the adopted approach to follow the experimental trends. In most cases there is an overestimation of the experimental values keeping a nearly constant error over the whole temperature range explored (Figure 75), while in others it is possible to see an underestimation of the same parameter.

Figure 75 Enthalpy of ulvospinel (left) and curospinel (right) as a function of temperature: comparison between calculated (blue line) and experimental (red points) values.

Also in the case of entropy the calculated values reproduce the trend of the experimental data with a good agreement. The percentage error is about 10% on average with the highest deviation for the MgAl_2O_4 of about 31%. The thermodynamic property calculated deviates from experimental data at high temperature (Figure 76) due to changes that this approach does not include. However, the measured error in the worst case at 1400K is of the order of 10% staying in acceptable range.

Figure 76 Entropy of ulvospinel (left) and curospinel (right) as a function of temperature: comparison between calculated (blue line) and experimental (red points) values.

5.2.1.2 Computational study on oxide layer

After the validation process, the computational study has been performed on the compounds which experimental investigations on corrosion phenomena due to liquid lead in LFRs suggest. In particular, the Fe-Cr spinel layer has been analysed both chemically and thermodynamically.

Crystal structure of spinel

Magnetite and chromite are two compounds of interest, because they are formed on steels exposed to liquid lead under proper oxygen concentrations. They both belong to the spinel family that is named after mineral MgAl_2O_4 which is precisely called Spinel (Sickafus et al. 1999). This class of crystals has a general formula AB_2O_4 that denotes cations (A, B) and anions (oxygen) positions in the crystalline structure (Figure 77). MgAl_2O_4 belong to the space group $\text{Fd}\bar{3}\text{m}$ (No. 227) with a tetrahedral primitive unit cell. As it is possible to see in the figure the repetition of four of primitive cell makes up conventional cubic cell, identified by a general symbol $\text{cf}56$.

Figure 77 Structure of spinel.

Using VASP with Monkhorst-Pack scheme based on $4 \times 4 \times 4$ k-points, lattice parameters have been calculated by means of a minimization of the ground state energy. The minimum of the curve (Figure 78) identifies the lattice parameter, after the geometric optimization, providing the value to compare with experimental one.

Figure 78 Ground state energy of MgAl_2O_4 as a function of lattice parameter.

A phenomenon, which characterizes spinel class, is the disorder process of cations. In order to take this effect into account, it is convenient to introduce an inversion parameter i , defined as the fraction of divalent metal cations that moves to octahedral from tetrahedral sites, in order to distinguish the type of distribution (Tielens et al. 2006):

where M and N are respectively bivalent and trivalent cations, while A and B identify tetrahedral (Td) and octahedral (Oh) sites. In the case of normal spinel i is set equal to 0, for inverse spinel $i=1$ and for partially inverse spinel $0 < i < 1$. It is possible to experimentally measure the inversion parameter by nuclear magnetic resonance, however with the help of simulations, an ideal structure can be studied in order to extrapolate representative information of the compounds. In particular, the inversion parameters can be analyzed with the only dependence of cations configuration and according to the limitation of VASP code. Inversion parameter has an important role not only for the characteristic dimension of the crystal but also for a lot of properties. This kind of influence is due to the position of cations in the structure and, considering the hypothesis of spherical atoms, to their radii values which are different for the case of bivalent or trivalent positive ions, the first larger than the second ones.

Spinel class under study is composed by transition metals of the fourth period. Those atoms have a specific valence electronic configuration that determines their physical-chemical properties. So external electronic configuration is definable using quantum numbers. Valence electrons are very important for compound formation because their configuration determines the type of bonds with other species.

To better describe the strong correlation between electrons in orbital d of the atom under study, the approach proposed by Dudarev et al. has been used exploiting DFT+U method as implemented in VASP code. This correction consists in adding two parameters: Hubbard (U) and Exchange (J) that correspond respectively to the averaged Coulomb and exchange interaction among electrons of angular momentum which are localized on the same atom. Typically, these values are evaluated principally in a semi-empirical way that is trying values until the results are in a good agreement with experimental data. But this kind of approach could be criticized because it would be ad hoc choice. In addition, another way implies DFT calculation for finding those parameters starting from energy relation between electrons in the simulated structure. In Dudarev approach $U_{\text{eff}} = U - J$ is also defined, and it is frequently reported in literature as U value. For the cases of interest, it is worth noting that, U_{eff} values applied in the simulations, are found in literature and they are referred to the constitutive elements (Zn, Fe, Cr, Ni) of magnetite, chromite, franklinite and trevorite, but contained in different compounds (such as ZnO, Cr₂O₃ etc.). The simulations computed, using the DFT+U method described above, show how it is possible to reduce the errors between calculated and measured lattice parameters.

U_{eff}	a exp [Å]	a cal [Å]	err%	U_{eff}	a exp [Å]	a cal [Å]	Err%
-		8.1694	2.7	-		8.1983	2.9375
2		8.2012	2.32	4.5		8.3788	0.8009
2.5		8.2088	2.23	5		8.4037	0.5062
3		8.5118	1.37	5.5		8.3979	0.5746
3.5	8.3963	8.5079	1.32	6	8.4465	8.3919	0.6461
3.8		8.5066	1.31	6.5		8.3852	0.7255
4		8.5249	1.53	7		8.4091	0.4418
4.5		8.5206	1.48	7.5		8.3704	0.9
5		8.5117	1.37	8		8.3621	0.9987

Table 15: Lattice parameter of magnetite (*left*) and franklinite (*right*) at different U parameter values. The reported values in the first line have been calculated without U parameter.

The results, shown in the Table , highlight an improvement in the evaluation of lattice parameters while regarding thermodynamics properties this approach supplies only a little enhancement. This difference could be related to the use of not specifically calculated values of U parameter. The discrepancy could be solved by a systematic study on the correct values for the spinel compounds, considering the reciprocal effect of atoms in Td and Oh sites.

Fe-Cr spinel in the oxide layer

In order to study such spinel compounds of general formula $\text{Fe}^{2+}\text{Fe}^{3+}_{(2-x)}\text{Cr}^{3+}_x\text{O}_4$, the work has been firstly addressed to reproduce the lattice parameters. Starting from magnetite, an inverse spinel type where Fe^{3+} and Fe^{2+} cations are randomly scattered in the tetrahedral and octahedral sites, Cr^{3+} has been added in the octahedral sites until chromite (FeCr_2O_4) has been obtained. It has to be underlined that the spinel crystal structure is cF56 showing 8 atoms in 2+ sites, 16 atoms in 3+ and 32 atoms of oxygen for normal spinel, while in the case of inverse spinel type the distribution is different but in the first approach the hypothesis of normal spinel has been assumed for the inverse type. Several simulations were performed by VASP using Monkhorst-Pack scheme based on 4x4x4 k-points grid for Brillouin-zone and employing GGA and L(S)DA+U approximations. Simulations of the $\text{Fe}^{2+}\text{Fe}^{3+}_{(2-x)}\text{Cr}^{3+}_x\text{O}_4$ structure were performed by changing the number of chromium atoms, as shown in Table , and the lattice parameters were derived. The values x is the result of a proportion between the effective number of Cr^{3+} present in the structure and the total number of cations in Oh for the stoichiometry (for example $16[\text{total number of cations in Oh}]:1[\text{number of Cr}^{3+}]=2[\text{stoichiometry of the general formula}]:x[\text{composition}]$).

Number of Fe ²⁺ cations	Number of Fe ³⁺ cations	Number of Cr ³⁺ cations	Number of O ²⁻ anions	Composition x
8	16	0	32	0
	15	1		0.125
	14	2		0.25
	13	3		0.375
	12	4		0.5
	11	5		0.625
	10	6		0.75
	9	7		0.875
	8	8		1
	7	9		1.125
	6	10		1.25
	5	11		1.375
	4	12		1.5
	3	13		1.625
	2	14		1.75
	1	15		1.875
0	16	2		

Table 16: Details of simulations: number of cations/anions in the crystalline unit and number of chromium atoms (x).

The lattice parameters calculated by simulations, reported in Figure 799 (right), were compared with the experimental ones (Figure 799 left). First, it can be noted that four composition regions can be identified in Figure 799 left, slightly different according to different authors. In general, in Region 1 ($x \approx 0-0.4$) the lattice parameter decreases, it is constant in Region 2 ($x \approx 0.4-0.8$), it increases in Region 3 ($x \approx 0.8-1.3$) and it decreases again in Region 4 ($x \approx 1.3-2$). The general trend of the calculated values of lattice parameter resembles the one obtained from the experimental data (Francombe et al. 1957, Yearian et al. 1954). The errors between experimental and calculated values are 0.1% - 2 %. Unexpected values of lattice parameter (local peak) were obtained at the lowest x values ($x \approx 0.125$) and symmetrically at compositions near to chromite ($x \approx 1.75$): this may depend on the rearrangement of crystal and electronic structure.

Figure 79 Experimental (left) and calculated (right) lattice parameter of $\text{Fe}^{2+}\text{Fe}^{3+}(2-x)\text{Cr}^{3+}_x\text{O}_4$ as a function of number of chromium atoms (x).

After the geometrical optimization, the enthalpy of formation of the compounds $\text{Fe}^{2+}\text{Fe}^{3+}_{(2-x)}\text{Cr}^{3+}_x\text{O}_4$ for $x=0$ to 2 at 298.15 K was evaluated, in order to identify which spinel compound is more probable to find under the magnetite layer. Taking into account the stoichiometry of the intermediate spinel and the VASP limitation on compositions (integer values), formation enthalpy is calculated using the following formula:

$$H_{for} = \frac{E_{comp}}{8} + [(2-x) + 1] \frac{E_{iron}}{2} + x \frac{E_{chromium}}{2} + c \frac{E_{oxygen}}{2}$$

where c is equal to 4, $[(2-x) + 1]$ and x are coefficients that indicate the number of each atom in the spinel compound. As shown in Figure 800, DFT-GGA simulations of mixed oxide $\text{Fe}^{2+}\text{Fe}^{3+}_{(2-x)}\text{Cr}^{3+}_x\text{O}_4$ enabled to identify $\text{Fe}_{1.5}\text{Cr}_{1.5}\text{O}_4$ as the most thermodynamically probable oxide composition.

Figure 80 Formation enthalpy as a function of the number of Chromium atoms x .

By inserting the vibrational frequencies and energetic contributions obtained from simulations of $\text{Fe}_{1.5}\text{Cr}_{1.5}\text{O}_4$ compound into the statistical thermodynamics equations, the thermodynamic parameters were estimated as a function of temperature, in particular heat capacity at both low and high temperature (Figure 81), enthalpy and entropy (Figure 82).

Figure 81 Heat capacity at low temperature (25 – 400 K, left) and at high temperature (298.15 -1400 K, right) of $\text{Fe}_{1.5}\text{Cr}_{1.5}\text{O}_4$ as a function of temperature.

Figure 82 Enthalpy (left) and entropy (right) of Fe_{1.5}Cr_{1.5}O₄ as a function of temperature (298.15 -1400 K).

Finally, preliminary investigations on more complex structures have been successfully performed. Indeed, experimental studies identified the formation of Plumboferrite ($n\text{PbO}-m\text{Fe}_2\text{O}_3$) in the oxide layer, and thus the prototype of such structure, magnetoplumbite $\text{PbFe}_{12}\text{O}_{19}$ (Figure 83), has been studied.

Figure 83 The hexagonal elementary cell of the magnetoplumbite structure (Shi et al. 2015).

The lattice parameter has been evaluated with an error of 5% with respect to the experimental data and then the accuracy further improved to 1% by applying the Dudarev et al. approach. As shown in Figure 84, the thermodynamic properties (enthalpy, entropy and heat capacity) have been determined as a function of temperature.

Figure 84 Heat capacity (top), enthalpy (middle) and entropy (bottom) of PbFe₁₂O₁₉ as a function of temperature.

Such preliminary calculations suggest the feasibility to study by the proposed approach much more complex systems, such as the compounds that could be formed at lead/steel interface under corrosive conditions. Theoretical and computational evaluations will be further compared to experimental evidences.

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6 FE-O INTERACTIONS IN LBE AND IN PB (SCK-CEN)

Introduction

Fe-O interaction is one of the most important chemical reactions in Pb and in LBE because the reaction determines the coolant chemistry at the interface between coolant and materials. In this study, we investigated Fe_3O_4 solubility product and Fe_2O_3 formation from Fe_3O_4 in LBE and in Pb.

6.1 MAGNETITE SOLUBILITY PRODUCT IN LBE

Experimental setup

The experimental setup consists of a lab-scale autoclave which can contain up to ca. 5.5 kg of stagnant LBE (Fig. 85). To avoid chemical interactions between the LBE and stainless steel, the LBE is contained in an alumina crucible. The crucible is placed inside a stainless steel container wrapped with electrical heaters. The spacing between the stainless steel container and the crucible is kept as small as possible.

Figure 85 Schematic cross section of the experimental setup

Two potentiometric oxygen sensors comprised of an yttria partially stabilized zirconia (YSZ) solid electrolyte and an air/LSM (Lanthanum strontium manganite) reference electrode are immersed into the LBE to control the Dissolved Oxygen Concentration (DOC) [1]. A stainless steel wire welded onto the autoclave lid is in contact with the LBE in order to complete the electric circuit of the sensors. One sensor is used to measure the potential difference between the reference electrode and the LBE. The measured potential difference can be directly linked to the DOC via the oxygen activity and Nernst's equation:

$$\Delta E = \frac{RT}{2F} \ln \frac{a_{\text{O}_2}}{a_{\text{O}(lbe)}} \quad (1)$$

with R the gas constant; F Faraday's constant; T temperature; a_{O_2} and $a_{\text{O}(lbe)}$ the activities of molecular oxygen in the air and atomic oxygen dissolved in LBE respectively.

Eq. (1) leads to the following correlation defining dissolved oxygen concentration in LBE (DOC) [2]:

$$C_{O(lbe)} = \exp\left(-7.966 + \frac{16284 - 23209\Delta E [\text{V}]}{T [\text{K}]}\right) [\text{wt. \%}] \quad (2)$$

A small flowrate of argon (Ar) or argon + 5 % hydrogen (Ar + H₂) is used to the cover gas space at small overpressure (100-150 mbar) to regulate the DOC in the LBE. Temperature is monitored by a K-type thermocouple inserted in one of the oxygen sensors and changed by a process controller Eurotherm Model 2416. An Agilent 34972A voltmeter measures every 60 seconds the potential difference.

The LBE used in the experiments was obtained from 5N Plus Belgium. Received LBE ingots were melted in a big melting tank exposed to air. Due to the lower density in respect to LBE, impurity oxides started to congregate on the LBE surface forming a floating oxide layer. After removal of the layer, the LBE for the experiments was collected from a pipe on the bottom of the tank to ensure higher purity.

Thermal cycling method

In an ideal case, the thermal cycling method assumes variation of temperature at constant total oxygen concentration. A trend of the DOC, measured during thermal cycling by an oxygen sensor, characterizes the state of LBE over temperature. A constant value of the DOC corresponds to the LBE system in which no oxygen sources or sinks are present, while sudden changes of the DOC trend – a drop or a lift – are believed to point to oxide transformation (e.g. formation or dissolution).

In practice, total oxygen concentration gradually increases during thermal cycling because of a small but continuous temperature-dependent oxygen in-leak, whose effect can be beneficially used to "scan" a region of the LBE "oxygen-temperature" map while cycling temperature in a given range. The opposite process, a small removal of oxygen by using an Ar + H₂ gas flow to the cover gas, is also feasible. Ar + H₂ purging is only effective at high temperatures (above 425 °C [3]), when oxygen in-leak is high, which allows for control of constant total oxygen concentration at lower temperatures. As long as the rate of net oxygen addition is small compared to changes of the DOC trend, experimental results can be considered accurate.

Fig. 86 shows two typical examples of a thermal cycling experiment: an experiment driven by oxygen in-leak (Fig. 86a) and an experiment with Ar + H₂ purging (Fig. 86b). A thermal cycling experiment is composed of thermal cycles which consist of heating segments and cooling segments. The arrows mark the direction of the experiment in time helping to notice the difference between cooling segments and heating segments. The black crosses mark the start of the experiments.

Figure 86 Examples of a thermal cycling experiment: the PbO line marks the oxygen solubility in LBE; the crosses – the start of the experiments; the arrows – the direction of the experiments in time; the dot markers – the drop of the DOC trend

In the high temperature region (above 400 °C – 430 °C) of a thermal cycle, no changes in the DOC are expected besides a slow increase or decrease depending on the experimental conditions (Ar or Ar + H₂ purging). However, in some conditions, as shown in Fig. 86a, a small decrease in the DOC is visible even though the experiment is driven by in-leak. This small effect could be caused by corrosion of the welded metal wire at high temperatures as it is only metal component in the setup.

The DOC trend in the region of concentrations higher than the oxygen saturation limit has been well-described in [4]: PbO nucleation is known to occur only after passing the saturation concentration with 10 °C – 20 °C, as visible in Fig. 86. Changes in the DOC below the PbO formation limit are expected to be caused by formation/dissolution of other oxides which are more stable than PbO. A beginning of such change (marked here by a black dot) corresponds to start of oxide formation/dissolution, and its height (shown by the vertical double-side arrow) characterizes a formed/dissolved amount of the oxide.

To analyse the trend of the DOC we use hereafter only cooling segments. The reason is that heating segments force us to deal with dissolution of several oxides starting from PbO simultaneously, thus raising the question how to distinguish between the complete dissolution of PbO and the start of another oxide dissolution. Conversely, cooling segments allow us to track the formation of oxides one after another by observing consecutive drops in the DOC trend.

Magnetite solubility product modelling

Aerts *et al.* [5] has demonstrated the importance of oxygen-iron interaction in the LBE bulk for the DOC control. They defined a first chemical interaction between dissolved oxygen and corrosion products in the LBE bulk – magnetite (Fe₃O₄) formation from dissolved iron and dissolved oxygen:

Based on the Gossé solubility data for iron in LBE [6], the Sievert constant of oxygen dissolution in LBE defined by *Lim et al. (2017)* [7] and the Gibbs free energy of magnetite formation provided by the HSC database [8], the HSC Outotech software is able to model the equilibrium behaviour of dissolved oxygen in LBE in a range of low oxygen concentration. Such equilibrium simulations are in a good agreement with the results of a thermal cycling experiment in stagnant LBE (Fig. 87).

Figure 87 Comparison of the thermal cycling simulations by HSC and results of a thermal cycling experiment. During simulations Fe content was assumed 1 ppmw. The experiment was carried out in stagnant LBE with 0.2 °C/min cooling rate and Ar cover gas. The PbO line represents the oxygen saturation limit. The Fe₃O₄ line corresponds to the DOC when LBE is saturated with Fe.

6.2 MAGNETITE TRANSITION TO HEMATITE IN LBE

Background

During thermal cycling experiments formation of an additional oxide, besides Fe₃O₄ and PbO, was detected in a region of the DOC near the oxygen saturation limit in pristine LBE (Fig. 88).

Figure 88 Thermal cycling experiment in pristine LBE: initial oxygen concentration was $1 \cdot 10^{-4}$ wt. %, temperature rate – $1 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}/\text{min}$, cover gas – Ar + H₂. The crosses mark the onset of the oxide formation; the colour area represents the uncertainty of the DOC measurement.

In order to describe the observed oxide formation, a hypothesis that it is hematite forming via the following chemical reaction was considered:

The onset points defined in different thermal cycling experiments were compared with the EOC calculated via the following formula derived from the equilibrium constant of the reaction (4):

$$\ln(kC_{O(lbe)}) = \frac{3\Delta G_{f, \text{Fe}_2\text{O}_3} - 2\Delta G_{f, \text{Fe}_3\text{O}_4}}{RT} \quad (5)$$

with k the Sievert constant, $\lg k = 3.12 - 7072 / T$ [6]; $\Delta G_{f, \text{Fe}_2\text{O}_3}$ and $\Delta G_{f, \text{Fe}_3\text{O}_4}$ the Gibbs free energy of hematite and magnetite formation respectively.

Thermodynamic data selected from different sources [8- 13] result in a broad range of the possible EOC of Fe₂O₃ formation (not shown here). This broad range stems from the formula (5) itself – subtraction of the multiplied by factor 3 and 2 Gibbs free energy of hematite and magnetite formation causes propagation of the uncertainty. It was identified that the contribution of the standard-state entropy, heat capacity values and Sievert constant to the uncertainty of the formula (5) are negligible compared to the contribution of the uncertainty of the standard-state enthalpy values. Therefore, the following expression was derived to estimate the uncertainty of the formula (5):

$$\Delta \ln C_{O(lbe)} = \frac{1}{RT} \sqrt{9(\Delta H_{\text{Fe}_2\text{O}_3}^{298.15\text{K}})^2 + 4(\Delta H_{\text{Fe}_3\text{O}_4}^{298.15\text{K}})^2} \quad (6)$$

with $H_{\text{Fe}_2\text{O}_3}^{298.15\text{K}}$ and $\Delta H_{\text{Fe}_3\text{O}_4}^{298.15\text{K}}$ the uncertainty of standard-state enthalpy of Fe₂O₃ and Fe₃O₄ respectively.

Fig. 89 compares the defined onset points from different experiments with the EOC calculated based on the JANAF and Barin [1] data since they show the best agreement with the experimental data. The grey shadowed area represents the uncertainty of the formula (5) calculated from the expression (4) with data given in JANAF ($\Delta H_{\text{Fe}_2\text{O}_3}^{298.15\text{K}} = \pm 1.3 \text{ kJ}$ and $\Delta H_{\text{Fe}_3\text{O}_4}^{298.15\text{K}} = \pm 0.8 \text{ kJ}$) [12].

Figure 89 Comparison of the defined onset with the EOC for Fe_2O_3 formation based on the thermodynamic data of JANAF and Barin [13, 12]. The grey shadowed uncertainty area was calculated based on the data of JANAF [12].

The onset points observed in experiments with different cooling rates (varied from 0.2 °C/min to 1 °C/min), cover gas (Ar or Ar+H₂) and different initial metal impurity content consistently show formation of the oxide presented on Fig. 88.

Experimental validation of hematite formation

In order to validate the hypothesis that the detected oxide is Fe_2O_3 forming via the reaction (4), an experiment with Fe addition to LBE was conducted. It was aimed at testing the following two statements derived from the assumed chemical reaction (4):

- Fe addition should not affect the EOC of the detected oxide formation because it is independent on the Fe concentration.
- added Fe is expected to increase the amount of the formed oxide because added Fe transforms to Fe_3O_4 via the chemical reaction (1), which in turn is a source of Fe_2O_3 .

Two experiments were conducted. The first experiment was carried out in LBE without Fe addition. The second experiment was performed in new LBE which was saturated with Fe by means of a pure iron bar submersed four times into the LBE at different temperatures and the DOC ($1 \cdot 10^{-6} \text{ wt. \%} - 1 \cdot 10^{-4} \text{ wt. \%}$). Each time the iron bare was exerted from the LBE at low oxygen concentration, around $1 \cdot 10^{-9} \text{ wt. \% DOC}$; consequently, the maximum expected amount of Fe added to the LBE due to the dissolution of Fe was estimated as 9.6 ppm Fe from the reaction (3). Formation of the detected oxide would consume up to $4.6 \cdot 10^{-5} \text{ wt. \% DOC}$.

In both experiments, the cooling rate was chosen as 0.2 °C/min to ensure the equilibrium state at every moment of time. Fig. 90 compares two thermal cycles of these experiments with the EOC calculated from the equation (5) based on the JANAF and Barin data.

Figure 90 Comparison of two experiments with different amount of iron.

The comparison of these two experiments validates the two statements formulated above:

- The position of the onset is the same for both experiments. It means the independence of the onset position from Fe concentration.
- The Fe addition causes the increase of the DOC drop. In addition to the first conclusion, it favours formation of the detected oxide from an Fe-containing oxide rather than from dissolved iron.

Thus, the detected oxide has been identified as hematite forming from magnetite via the reaction (2).

6.3 MAGNETITE SOLUBILITY PRODUCTS IN PB

Lim et al. (2021) [14] has determined the Sievert constant of oxygen dissolution in lead:

$$\lg k = 2.43 - \frac{6700}{T}, \quad (623 \text{ K} < T < 823 \text{ K})$$

In addition to the known solubility data of iron in Pb defined by Gossé [6] and the Gibbs free energy of magnetite formation provided by the HSC database, the equilibrium behaviour of dissolved oxygen in Pb in a range of low oxygen concentration can be modelled in the same way as in LBE (Fig. 87). The results are presented in Fig. 91.

Figure 91 Thermal cycling simulations of Pb by HSC. The Fe content was set to 10 ppmw. The Fe_3O_4 line corresponds to the DOC when LBE is saturated with Fe.

Magnetite to hematite transition in Pb

Based on the results of the experimental campaign presented in section 2, the Barin thermodynamic data for Fe_2O_3 and Fe_3O_4 have been selected to model hematite formation in Pb. However, in order to illustrate the difference between thermodynamic data, the same simulation was performed using the thermodynamic data of the HSC database (Fig. 92).

Figure 92: Thermal cycling simulations of Pb by HSC. The Fe content was set to 10 ppmw. The two cooling segments pictured with markers in Fig. 7b follows Fe_2O_3 formation line without reaching the oxygen saturation limit. The Fe_2O_3 lines were calculated based on the equation (5).

Fig. 92b shows two examples of cooling segments (blue and green line with markers) when formation of Fe_2O_3 prevents system from reaching the oxygen saturation limit. However, when an initial DOC is high enough to complete Fe_2O_3 formation (which depends on Fe content in the system), Pb reaches its saturation (small red transitions from the blue dashed-dotted line to the black dashed line). If the DOC is even higher, then, similar to the case pictured in Fig. 92a, Pb reaches its saturation before formation

of Fe_2O_3 becomes thermodynamically favourable. Based on the experimental results of section 2 for LBE, one would expect the situation of Fig. 92a rather than that of Fig. 92b in Pb.

Summary

Two Fe-O chemical reactions have been identified in LBE – magnetite formation and hematite formation. Equilibrium of both reactions can be modelled based on the available thermodynamic data, even though the thermodynamic data for hematite formation are subject to further investigation.

Magnetite transition to hematite taking place in a high DOC region before the oxygen saturation limit might result in change of the passivation layer on the surface of stainless steels leading to change in the corrosion rate. Therefore, experimental investigation of the influence of hematite formation on corrosion process in LBE might extend the understanding of the corrosion phenomenon. Fortunately, the DOC for hematite formation is independent on metal impurity composition of LBE being only dependent on temperature, which makes it simple to track Fe_2O_3 formation in LBE in terms of the DOC. This feature allows one to easily adjust temperature and the DOC of LBE to avoid or initiate Fe_2O_3 formation for a specific set of corrosion experiments.

Based on the results obtained in LBE, the same reactions were modelled in lead. The results of the equilibrium calculations indicate that while magnetite forms at the DOC higher than in LBE, hematite formation is not relevant for lead.

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7 CONCLUSIONS

In the frame of GEMMA project, task 4.4, the corrosion of model FeCr and FeCr Ni alloys in Pb and PbBi eutectic liquid metals was evaluated to the aim of gather information on the mechanisms of corrosion of technological steels in heavy liquid metals. An overview of the thermodynamic description of the Pb-Bi-Fe-Cr-Ni-O system and subsections has been produced in support of the experimental work. A modeling work from first principles of the FeCrO system and its interaction with Pb was then carried out. Finally, a study was conducted on the Fe-O system in liquid lead and lead bismuth.

The outcome of the corrosion experimental campaigns is summarized as follow:

Tests FeCr in LBE:

- Measurements performed on samples exposed at 450°C show the presence of a very thin oxide slowly growing and no dissolution attack at any time. The oxide resulted protective at all the times of exposure, nevertheless, increasing the time of exposure and starting at 2500h it was observed the development of spots, spread all over the sample surface, where there was a change in the oxidation mechanism and a dual layer oxide developed.
- The magnetite spots have circular shape and looks like rosettes over the FeCr oxide that covers the sample.
- In the dual layer spots, below the FeCr oxide growing inward it was observed the development of an internal oxidation zone.
- Outside of the dual layer spots, the growth rate of the oxide in 18 Cr alloy is much slower than the rate of technological 9Cr ferritic martensitic steels (F82H, EM10, P91) as reported in the literature.
- Increasing the temperature to 550°C it was observed the failure of the the oxide and the start of the dissolution attack
- The dissolution measured as depth of the zone penetrated by the LBE is faster increasing the temperature
- The element dissolved in the LBE is chromium.

Figure 93 Trend of the oxide thickness of the FeCr alloy in lead at 450. The plot reports the values relative to F82H, EM10 and P91 steel at 10-6 and 10-8 from the Handbook on Lead-bismuth Eutectic Alloy and Lead Properties, Materials Compatibility, Thermal-hydraulics and Technologies – 2007 Edition.

Figure 94 Trend of the depth of the dissolution attack for the FeCr alloy in lead at 550.

Tests FeCrNi in LBE:

- At the two temperatures tested the dissolution attack started after a very short time of exposure
- The dissolution measured as depth of the zone penetrated by the LBE and /or Ni depletion is faster increasing the temperature. Often it is observed the Ni depletion without HLM penetration to indicate a possible dissolution mechanism without the direct contact of the steel with the liquid metal.
- The elements dissolved in the LBE are nickel and chromium.
- The Cr dissolution is slower and more gradual, it is always observed a Cr concentration decreasing gradient in going toward the surface of the steel in the Ni depleted zone
- The dissolution rate measured in the FeCrNi alloy is much higher than that measured in the FeCr alloy. Higher than 1500 μm at 5000h for FeCrNi vs 50 μm vs measured in FeCr.
- The Corrosion rates of the model alloy result much higher compared with the data reported in the literature for the parent 316 SS (see figure 95 below)

Figure 95 Trend of the depth of the dissolution attack for the FeCrNi alloy in lead at 450°C and 550°C compared with the literature data at 550°C for AISI 316 SS.

Tests FeCr in Lead:

- The dissolution corrosion has never been observed in both 450°C and 550°C tests
- It is observed the growth of a dual oxide with thickness growing with the time of exposure and temperature.

Figure 96 Trend of the total thickness of the oxide grown versus time on FeCr alloy at 450°C and 550°C

- The ratio of the thickness of the sublayers is not constant over time, the average ratio is 0,85 at 450°C and 0,91 at 550°C but the for each temperature the measurements at the times sampled show large deviations from the average.

Tests FeCrNi in Lead:

- In tests performed at 450°C It is observed the growth of a dual oxide with thickness growing with the time of exposure and temperature.
- Figure 97 below shows the trend of the inner and outer oxide layer thickness varying the times of exposure.
- The ratio of the thickness inner/outer layer at 450°C is variable with average 0,94.
- In the tests at 450°C the thickness of the dissolution layer is always zero in all the times of exposure sampled.

Figure 97 Trend of the inner and outer oxide layer thickness varying the times of exposure

- In tests performed at 550°C also, it is observed the growth of a dual oxide with thickness growing with the time of exposure and temperature.
- Figure 98 below shows the trend of the inner and outer oxide layer thickness varying the times of exposure at 550°C.
- The plot of the inner and outer oxide layer thickness vs. time show the same non monotonic behavior for the two temperature tested with a minimum around 200h exposure.
- The samples exposed at 550°C show a dissolution attack with non-uniform behavior: the measurements for each exposure time show extremely variable penetration values from point to point and many points where dissolution is zero

Figure 98 Trend of the inner and outer oxide layer thickness varying the times of exposure at 550°C.

Tests FeCrNi in Lead at 500°C for 1000h and varying the oxygen concentration

The table below (table 9 pag 37) summarizes the material degradation detected on the examined cross sections of FeCrNi sample tested. The measurements performed in FeCrNi Model Alloy tested in LBE at 500 °C and different oxygen contents are summarized in the table below (Table 9 pag 37). The oxide layer has been found in samples exposed at the maximum oxygen concentration, 10⁻⁵ wt.%. It consists of a Fe-based outer layer and a Fe-Cr spinel inner layer. Both layers were not a compact oxide layer due to some penetration of LBE eutectic. In addition, some points with a relative slight Ni enrichment was observed obtained below the oxide layer, as consequence of the chromium depletion close to the spinel oxide. For lower oxygen concentrations it is reported the dissolution corrosion with depth increasing with the the decrease of the oxygen concentration. In the case of the material dissolution and the associated LBE penetrations, the EDX mapping have shown that both chromium and nickel dissolution take place.

	FeCrNi Model Alloys		
	10 ⁻⁵ wt.%. Oxide layers	10 ⁻⁷ wt.%. Dissolution	10 ⁻⁸ wt.%. Dissolution
Examination	Oxide layers	Dissolution	Dissolution
Average size (µm)	7.5	49	65
Maximum size (µm)	11	120	110
Maximum root (µm)		209	168

Table 9 pag 37

General observations:

- Some characterization has been performed in both samples polished and as received: it was generally observed a similar behaviour with same corrosion rate with a delay in the non-polished samples.

Structural and thermodynamic data in the FeCrNiPbBiO system and theoretical work

An overview of the structural and thermodynamic data in the FeCrNiPbBiO system has been given and preliminary investigations have been performed on the simulation of complex oxide structures of iron and lead by first principles. This preliminary work has been successfully performed and demonstrated the ability to simulate the behavior magnetoplumbite PbFe₁₂O₁₉ as prototype of Plumboferrites (nPbO-mFe₂O₃) in the oxide layer. The lattice parameter has been evaluated with an error of 1%. The thermodynamic properties (enthalpy, entropy and heat capacity) have been determined as a function of temperature. Such preliminary calculations suggest the feasibility to study by the proposed approach much more complex systems, such as the compounds that could be formed at lead/steel interface under corrosive conditions.

Finally, a study on the Fe-O interaction in Pb and in LBE has been carried out. The Fe-O reactions in the melt are important because determine the coolant chemistry at the interface between coolant and steel. In the study here presented it was investigated the Fe₃O₄ solubility product and Fe₂O₃ formation from Fe₃O₄ in LBE and in Pb. Two Fe-O chemical reactions have been identified in LBE – magnetite formation and hematite formation. It is shown that the equilibrium of both reactions can be modelled based on the available thermodynamic data, nevertheless the thermodynamic data for hematite formation should be subject to further investigation. Magnetite transition to hematite taking place in a high dissolved oxygen concentration region before the oxygen saturation limit might result in change of the passivation layer on the surface of stainless steels leading to change in the corrosion rate. The same reactions have been modelled in lead and indicate that while magnetite forms at a dissolved oxygen concentration higher than in LBE, hematite formation is not relevant for lead.